

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D6.1 POLICY CONDITIONS AND CATALOGUES OF EXISTING SOIL HEALTH ECONOMIC AND POLICY INCENTIVES

Policy conditions and catalogues of existing soil health economic and policy incentives

Summary

The issue of soil health is increasingly at the center of public and political discourse at European and national level. The social and environmental cost of soil degradation is estimated at EUR 50 billion per year in Europe alone, demonstrating the importance of soil in sustaining livelihoods, supporting biodiversity, and regulating the Earth's climate.¹ To date, efforts to place a monetary value on the ecosystem services provided by healthy soil have been rare.² It is crucial to reconsider the concept of healthy soil and to make the business community, politicians and public administration see soil as an investment opportunity for high quality services that are environmentally and resource friendly.

Regulatory policies, legislative frameworks, financial instruments, and economic models are the key tools to promote and facilitate public and private investment in healthy soil. In particular, the review of the policy and legislative framework at different scales of government offers an opportunity to understand the mechanisms to encourage the maintenance and further diffusion of techniques that improve soil health. A greater understanding of the actual effects of policies and incentives on soil health will improve understanding of the effectiveness of policies and incentives to maintain and restore soil health and will also serve as a basis for developing and improving the implementation of soil health policies and certification schemes.

The InBestSoil project aims to co-create a framework for investments in soil health preservation and restoration by developing a system for the economic valuation of the ecosystem services provided by healthy soil and the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentives. By analyzing policy requirements, barriers and enabling factors, as well as economic incentive programs aiming at sustainable soil management and preservation/restoration of soil health, the existing policies and economic incentives for soil health were reviewed through horizontal mapping and semi-structured interview mapping. The analysis helps to establish what types of methods are used to assess the effectiveness of soil intervention methods, the models and indicator analyses performed and other types of factors influencing the performance of public and private investment promotion in soil health.

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Table of contents

1	Introduction	5
2	Literature and desk review	7
2.1	Mapping Policy and Regulatory Instruments	8
2.1.1	Methods	8
2.1.2	Results of the review	9
2.1.3	Conclusions	19
2.2	Mapping Financial and Economic Instruments	20
2.2.1	Methods	20
2.2.2	Results	21
2.2.3	Conclusions	43
3	Ex-post performance assessment of selected instruments	43
3.1	Method	44
3.2	Discussion	45
3.2.1	Understanding of and experience with types of soil pressures and soil degradation	46
3.2.2	Benefits and opportunities of policies or financial mechanisms that consider protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of soil health	49
3.2.3	Barriers and challenges in implementing soil health policies and economic instruments	56
3.2.4	Trade-offs and synergies in the development and implementation of policies and economic instruments that take into account protection, rehabilitation and restoration of soil	61
3.3	Conclusions	65
4	Conclusions and Outlook	66
4.1	Expected European legislative steps	66
4.2	Recommendations for the LLs and LHs	69
4.3	Summary	69
5	References	71

1 Introduction

The European Commission proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law), which was issued in July 2023, recognizes that healthy soils are crucial for the EU economy, society and environment. Indeed, the literature has defined soil health as the ability of the soil to function as a vital living system to support plants, animals and humans.³⁻⁷ For the EU, the availability of healthy and fertile soils and land is crucial in the transition towards a sustainable bioeconomy. For this purpose, farmers can receive financial support for certain practices under EU legislation.⁶ Moreover, due to their ability to capture and store carbon, healthy soils contribute to the achievement of the EU's objectives on climate change. Soils are essential ecosystems that deliver valuable services that are vital to humans and the environment, such as safe, nutritious and sufficient food, biomass, clean water, nutrients cycling, carbon storage and a habitat for biodiversity.^{3,8,9} Indeed, soils contain one-quarter to one-third of all living organisms on the planet which contribute to a wide range of services essential to the sustainable functioning of all ecosystems (also called soil functions).^{3,8,10} Soil is thus crucial for fighting climate change, land degradation and desertification, for protecting human health, safeguarding biodiversity and ecosystems and ensuring food security.¹¹

The scientific literature has shown an increasing interest in the topic of policy, financial and economic instruments in relation to healthy soil. Soil is influenced by different types of pressures, such as physical or mechanical, chemical or material and biological, which interact with each other. From the perspective of policy instruments, types of interventions to address these pressures may include reducing sources of pollution, setting limits on harmful activities and sustainable land use. Sustainably using the soil may refer to both land cover, including for example species, and land use and practices, such as techniques. Policy instruments that deal with protection, restoration, and restoration of soil health at multiple scales and levels are understood as the means and measures that preserve and enhance soil as a natural resource. In addition, the multi-level soil health innovation system, which includes the definition of hard constraints, such as targets, forms of compensation, such as credits, and incentives, such as payments, represent the frameworks for the investigation of scientific literature and policies that operate according to soil conservation and protection objectives.

Financial solutions operate in different sectors such as agricultural, urban, forestry, watershed and general, and with respect to different pressures regarding soil services, functions, and properties. Financial instruments that operate in the context of the preservation of natural resources are developed starting from complex systems, where the desired results combine with the characteristics of each local context. The scientific literature through theoretical and empirical analysis highlights the fragmented nature of the soil conservation and restoration topic in different policy and financial declinations. In this context there is room for further research to understand how to implement a comprehensive and coherent policy framework that can promote a range of financial solutions. Financial instruments for soil health include price-based instruments, quantity instruments, debt/equity instruments, regulatory instruments, and insurance instruments. There is

a clear prevailing argument in favor of price-based instruments, which essentially place a monetary value on the land resource, such as economic incentives, compensation schemes and payments for ecosystem services.

International soil governance is fragmented. Indeed, in contrast to other environmental topics (such as air, climate, biodiversity, water, and pollutants), none of the different international instruments and institutions has a mandate specifically for protecting soil or provides an overarching or comprehensive framework for soil governance. However, the SDG "land degradation neutrality" is useful for guiding national policies and further work.¹² Similarly, despite the increasing awareness of the significance of soils and efforts to design a protection framework for soils, soils do not have binding instruments at the EU level. Instead, soil protection is directly and indirectly addressed across a wide range of EU policy instruments, including those focused on water, biodiversity, air, waste, and climate change. Moreover, Member States implement the EU policy with different degrees of flexibility, and they have also adopted their own national initiatives aside from legal or policy requirements at the EU level, such as soil protection laws or legislation protecting agricultural soils from construction.¹³

The purpose of this deliverable is conducting a mapping review of International, European, national, and regional policy requirements and incentives aiming at or encouraging management and investments in soil health. An extensive review of the scientific literature was conducted with the aim of identifying the economic instruments and policies that were most closely investigated on a theoretical and empirical level. The resulting catalogue of instruments represented the knowledge base shared with the experts, who contributed their insights to integrate the issues that should be considered in legislative and policy implementation. Local laboratories (LL and LH) are provided with some guidelines that help identify the social, technical, and commercial factors of success in terms of governance, with the aim of streamlining the value proposition of soil health improvement schemes for develop specific policies and recommendations for upscaling.

The report is structured as follows:

Section 2 "Literature and desk review" introduces the general task of the present report, explains the protocols designed to perform the reviews, provides extended analysis of the main policy and economic instruments gathered from the literature review and summarize the implementation and shortcomings. The section also emphasizes the results of the review with respect to the degree of depth, approaches and models used in the scientific literature and applied to the investigation of the main policy and economic instruments in the context of healthy soil.

Section 3 "Ex-post performance" of selected instrument, is dedicated to the collection of views and interpretations on existing policy and financial mechanisms supporting protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of healthy soil. The section explains how the interview process was conducted, the structure of the interview, how many participants were involved and from which country. The section also emphasizes the linkages, opportunities, and barriers among the different LLs and LHs, in terms of future improvement and development of more cohesive and comprehensive policy and economic instruments.

Section 4 "Conclusion and Outlook" provides a summary of the key findings and insights from the analysis conducted. The section also outlines the expected European legislation steps, recommendations for the Living Labs (LLs) and Light Houses (LHs).

2 Literature and desk review

The scoping review aims to map the current landscape of peer-reviewed and grey literature on policy incentives and nudges contributing to preserving and restoring soil health. This review explores what types of solutions are applied to address protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of soil at multiple governmental levels. Therefore, the study aims to provide better understanding on the features of legal, policy and economic instruments and their implementation challenges. The study selects the instruments matching the scope of the LHs and LLs and provides recommendations for future solution designs.

The study sets the following key research questions to guide the scoping review:

1. What are policy requirements, barriers, and enablers as well as economic incentive schemes delivering on sustainable soil management and preserving/restoring soil health?
2. What are the existing policies and economic incentives in place that operate on the issue of soil health?
3. What are the existing European, national, and regional (in LHs and LLs) policy incentives and nudges contributing to preserving and restoring soil health?

In order to investigate these questions, this section is structured in two main subsections about regulatory (Section 2.1) and financial instruments (Section 2.2). As regulatory instruments, this review considers the following typology: legislation and regulations including restrictions on harmful practices, land-use planning and soil conservation measures; standards and guidelines establishing minimum requirements and best practices for soil management and conservation. As economic instruments, this review considers the following typology: financial incentives such as grants, subsidies, or tax incentives; market-based instruments creating markets for soil ecosystem services, allowing for the trading of soil credits or the payment of ecosystem services related to soil conservation and restoration; pricing mechanisms taxes or levies on activities that contribute to soil degradation; tradable permits introducing a system where permits for certain soil-related activities, such as land-use changes or soil contamination, can be bought, sold, or traded. In terms of methods (Sections 2.1.1 and 2.2.1), the search strategy implies the identification of relevant databases and sources, the search terms and keywords, the inclusion and exclusion criteria for study selection. The study selection consists of the screening of titles and abstracts, a full-text assessment based on inclusion criteria and the data extraction process. The results of the review (Sections 2.1.2 and 2.2.2) provide an extended analysis of the main policy instruments sorted by the governmental level (i.e., international, EU and national) and of the main financial instruments sorted

by typology (such as incentives, PES). The conclusions (Sections 2.1.3 and 2.2.3) summarise the implementation and shortcomings of those instruments.

2.1 Mapping Policy and Regulatory Instruments

2.1.1 Methods

As Section 2 explained, Subsection 2.1 focuses on mapping the European, national and regional policy requirements aiming at or encouraging the management of soil health. In order to do that, this study applies a scoping review with the aim of understanding what types of regulatory solutions are implemented to ensure protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of soil at multiple governmental levels.

The search strategy implied that relevant databases and sources were identified. The peer-reviewed literature was searched and accessed via bibliographic databases, including Scopus, Web of science, Google Scholar and ResearchRabbit. Those bibliographic databases were selected in order to perform the most comprehensive coverage of available publications. However, they use different selection criteria. Therefore, there may be a different search result. The eligibility criteria for peer-reviewed and grey literature referred to: eligible publication type, publication characteristics, regulation, and legislation characteristics. In terms of type, the study considered peer reviewed journal articles, books, and their chapters. In terms of characteristics, both publications and regulations/legislation were in English. The publication and regulations/legislation status considered were respectively published and in force. The publication years considered was 2010–2023. The publication and regulations/legislation geographical borders included global, European Union and LH/LL countries, i.e., Croatia, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland, Latvia. The study examined land and soil as primary subject of regulations and legislation which included international agreements and policies as well.

The study selection started with the download of legal and policy instruments (n= 52 EU level; n= 22 global level; n =99 national level from FAOLEX) as an EXCEL file. After selecting primary and secondary legislation/policy, initial research of publications was conducted by using the bibliographic databases, such as Google search and Google Scholar. The first set of keywords/tags for Scopus search included: soil conservation; soil restoration; soil rehabilitation; soil protection; soil quality; soil pollution; soil degradation; soil erosion; land use. Based on the identified keywords, the following search string has been constructed for legislation and policy: "soil protection" or "soil restoration" or "soil rehabilitation" or "soil conservation" and "policy" or "best practice collection" or "guidance" or "regulation" or "legislation" or "strategy" or "directive". The list of articles was screened using keywords in the search strings, and the final results was manually screened by reading the abstracts of the results using the following criteria: referring to soil health and quality; referring to protection, rehabilitation, restoration (out of the many publications focusing on resource management and biodiversity conservation); referring to policy, legislation, regulation, best

practice collection, guidance, strategy, directive. Search results were exported to HubMeta in order to avoid duplication. The papers that were considered suitable for the full text phase were 148. In the full text review, the team of reviewers worked by reading the papers in full, extrapolating the information necessary to the report. Data were extracted through a combination of automated and manual full text screening after all relevant articles have been included (60 in total). Data were organized and reviewed based on the objective of the study (See Section 2). Affinities, patterns, and themes were identified, and findings are summarized in the following section.

2.1.2 Results of the review

Soil degradation is defined as a change in soil health status resulting in a diminished capacity of the ecosystem to provide goods and services for its beneficiaries.¹⁴ Soil degradation causes include agricultural, industrial, and commercial pollution; loss of arable land due to urban expansion, overgrazing, and unsustainable agricultural practices; and long-term climatic changes.¹⁵ Therefore, soil is affected by different types of pressures, such as physical or mechanical, chemical or material and biological, which interact among each other.¹⁶ Types of interventions for addressing such pressures may include: reducing sources of pollution, setting limits on harmful activities (such mining) and sustainable using the soil (land cover and practices) (Section 2.1.3).

The review explored how soil is degraded, by identifying the main pressures on soil and related types of interventions at multiple governmental levels, including global, EU and national (Section 2.1.2.1). The review introduced a degradation scale in order to examine legal and policy instruments aimed at the protection, restoration, and rehabilitation of soil at multiple governmental levels (Section 2.1.2.2). Finally, the review focused on business innovation by selecting legal and policy mechanisms setting hard constraints, such as targets, compensation forms, such as credits, and incentives, such as PES (Section 2.1.2.3).

2.1.2.1 Pressures on soil (how soil is degraded) & types of intervention

As the previous section introduced, soil is affected by several different types of pressures at all scales. The literature analysed the types of instruments applied to soil governance at different levels, from global to local,¹⁷ Jürges and Hansjürgens, 2018 identify regulations and laws to prohibit certain actions that may degrade land, such as pollution, by enforcing through penalties for infringement or facilitating through financial support, e.g. farming subsidies, PES or C credits.¹⁷ Soil pollution affects soil fertility which threatens food security and also poses risks to human health, both indirectly through the consumption of contaminated food and drinking water, and directly through exposure to contaminated soil.¹⁸ Since the first industrial revolution from the industrialised Western countries to the emerging industrialised Asia and other parts of the world, contaminated land has been rapidly expanding.¹⁹ In this context, the first international instrument which covers soil pollution more broadly and not in relation to specific pollutants is relatively recent, i.e. the 2017 UNEA Resolution.²⁰ In Europe, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the recent Green Deal instruments, i.e. the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the Farm to Fork Strategy (F2F), aim to

reduce fertilisers by 20%, nutrient losses by at least 50%, reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides use by 50% and hazardous pesticides by an additional 50% and increase organic farms to 25% by 2030 to prevent soil pollution and, on the other hand, enhance the use of organic fertilisers.²¹

Among the most common causes of soil contamination caused by human activity, the FAO highlights industry, mining, military activities, waste – which includes technological waste – and wastewater management, farming, stock breeding and the building of urban and transport infrastructures.²² The United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) is the main international instrument dealing with limiting harmful activities to the soil.²³ The Agenda 2030 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement on Climate Change also indirectly consider this issue. At EU level, there are indirect secondary measures dealing with human activities which are harmful for soil health, including the Water Framework Directive²⁴ and the National Emission Ceilings Directive (NECD)²⁵.

The review identifies sustainably using the soil as another type of interventions to soil degradation. Sustainably using the soil may refer to both land cover, including for example species, and land use and practices, such as techniques (for example ploughing). Land cover refers to what overlays or currently covers the ground, such as areas of vegetation (trees, bushes, fields, lawns), bare soil, hard surfaces (rocks, buildings) and wet areas and bodies of water (watercourses, wetlands)²⁶. The definition of land cover is fundamental, because in many existing classifications and legends it is confused with land use which refers to the arrangements, activities and inputs people undertake in a certain land cover type to produce, change or maintain it.²⁷ Jürges et al., 2018 identify restrictions on development involving conversion of use, by enforcing laws based on zoning, e.g. National Parks, or more general laws, by following guidance, based on ad hoc site evaluation, such as an environmental impact assessment (EIA), by publicly acquiring the land, such as land trusts; by financial support.¹⁷ Moreover, the study looks at generic incentives to preserve land or to enhance its ecosystem services value in the form of taking land out of agricultural production, purely for the purpose of conservation, e.g. EU set-aside; converting an area of intensive agricultural production (arable cropping) to more extensive agricultural production (such as pasture, silvopasture or agroforestry) or forestry; declining to develop or intensify the use of uncultivated land that could otherwise be legally developed or intensified, in order to maintain ecological or ecosystem services value.¹⁷

At the international level, the main indicator under the UNCCD which has been developed so far is "proportion of land that is degraded over total land area", which involves land cover and land cover change, land productivity and carbon stocks in and above the soil. Delibas et al., 2021 explains that UN Convention to Combat Desertification formulated the goal to achieve zero net land degradation under 'Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN)' framework.²⁸ The framework calls for a paradigm shift in land management policies and practices that focuses on compensating the expected loss of productive land through recovery. Moreover, SDG15.3 focuses on the achievement of LDN by

introducing land management practices that avoid the loss of healthy land and maintain or improve the land's productivity (SDSN, 2015).¹² The United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) also indirectly deal with the land use.¹² The Ramsar Convention on Wetlands also calls upon countries to "improve management practices of those peatlands and other wetland types that are significant carbon stores, or have the ability to sequester carbon".²⁹ Both the UNFCCC and the Kyoto Protocol of 1997 adopted rules on reporting and accounting for emissions from land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF).¹² In 2018, the Paris Agreement (PA) adopted a transparency framework which, inter alia, included rules for reporting on and accounting for land use and land-use change.³⁰

At the EU level, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is the main EU tool regulating soil management practices and the post-2020 CAP provides several tools to promote the sustainable use of soils and safeguard soil biodiversity. For instance, proposing eco-schemes, which are a list of voluntary agricultural practices beneficial for the environment and for soil biodiversity (decided upon by the Member States).²¹ The CAP includes incentives for landowners to implement land management practices that limit soil erosion. The GAEC standards aim to contribute to the maintenance of the landscape, water protection, climate action and management practices that increase the levels of soil organic matter and avoid soil erosion.³¹ The recent EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 also focuses on the transition to fully sustainable agricultural practices, as biodiversity conservation is crucial for food security and can bring direct economic benefits to many sectors.³¹

At national level, Stankovics et al., 2018 highlight that only a few Member States have implemented national regulations for soil biodiversity conservation supporting sustainable farming practices.³² In the Murcia region, Spain, Calatrava et al., 2011 analyze the different policy options available for irrigated and non-irrigated agriculture and their ability to address land degradation.³³ The study reveals that, although agricultural policies have favoured some adoption of less intensive tillage, conservation structures and water quality control, some of the existing agricultural policy measures should be better adapted to regional conditions, while others should be further financed.³³ In Italy, Di Bene et al., 2022 affirms that more in-depth analysis based on intensive irrigated cereal-based cultivation systems could support policy makers to distinguish between practices related to arable land farms more complex ones that involve structural changes to the entire farm and cropping systems.³⁴ This distinction would allow to develop the implementation of eco-schemes, looking at production contexts, and to plan voluntary actions for rural development that could lead further agro-ecological transitions towards sustainable and diversified agri-food systems.³¹ The Netherlands addresses compaction and the loss of biodiversity through the erosion regulation which defines important measures for agricultural activities with the aim to protecting the soil by ploughing and catch crops.³²

2.1.2.2 Soil degradation scale

After explaining how soil is degraded and what types of interventions are in place at different levels, this review explores the soil degradation scale in order to identify policy instruments dealing with the protection, restoration and rehabilitation of soil health at multiple scales and levels. Soil protection is the application of means and measures to preserve and improve the soil as a natural resource, to restore it in case of damages and protect it from destruction, degradation, and pollution.³⁵ Indeed, soil restoration is the process of improving the structure, microbial life, nutrient density, and overall carbon levels of soil.³⁶ Rehabilitation is required when the land is already degraded to such an extent that the original use is no longer possible and the land has become practically unproductive.¹⁵

In 1992, the UN Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro, produced three major soft law documents which indirectly play an important role in soil protection, i.e., the Statement of Forest Principles, the Rio Declaration and Agenda 21.³⁷ While the literature pointed out the lack of a specific soil convention, it recognises that binding instruments in other fields of environmental policy might have consequences on the use of the soils, especially the UNCCD, the CBD and the UNFCCC.²⁹ The UNCCD, adopted in June 1994, encourages countries to adopt a broad range of measures to avoid, reduce, and reverse land degradation.³⁸ These measures include planning, regulation, and sustainable land management, "combined with localized action to reverse past degradation, through land restoration and rehabilitation, to achieve a state of no net loss of healthy and productive land".³⁹ However, UNCCD measures mainly focus only on soil erosion, soil contamination and salinization.³⁷ The UNCBD did not specifically deal with the soil as a natural resource to be protected, but also had a major influence on the scientific understanding of soil biota through the protection of ecosystems and biodiversity.³⁷ By recognising the significant role of peatlands for climate change mitigation, the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands called upon countries to reduce the degradation, improve restoration, and develop management practices of those peatlands which are important carbon stores.⁴⁰ Under the UNFCCC, the Kyoto Protocol particularly stresses the importance of taking into account soils and sustainable land use, as they play a critical role in influencing the carbon cycle and, thus, in regulating atmospheric concentration of GHG.⁴¹ The Paris Agreement only indirectly addresses soil protection in the general context of climate change.¹² Soil also plays a central role in many of the 17 SDGs, especially the first target of Goal 15 requires a legislative intervention for restoration.⁴² Keesstra et al., 2016 urge significant actions if water-related ecosystems are not be restored by 2030 in line with SDG 6.6 since soils also slow to change.⁴³

Similarly, at EU level, soil is regulated under a complex system of instruments coming from different sectors, such as water, biodiversity, pollution. However, the new Soil Strategy sets medium-term objectives to be achieved by 2030 and long-term objectives to be achieved by 2050, building on synergies and common goals in other environmental areas.²¹ To achieve the ultimate objective of having all soils in healthy condition by 2050, the proposed Soil Monitoring Law provides

a harmonised definition of soil health, a comprehensive and coherent monitoring framework and rules on sustainable soil management and remediation of contaminated sites.⁴⁴

So far, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and its application by Member States has largely influenced the sustainable management of agricultural soils in the EU, hence their protection.⁴⁵ It comprises two main elements: market price and direct income payments (Pillar 1), and incentive payments targeting rural development (Pillar 2).⁴⁶ Cross compliance is a mandatory measure whose main purpose is to promote more sustainable agriculture.⁴⁷ Cross-compliance is the creation of a link between the receipt of direct income support payments by a farmer and his/her compliance with certain rules for the protection of the environment, food safety, animal health, animal welfare, public health plant health and environmental condition.⁴⁸ Under cross compliance rules, farmers' failure to comply with those rules can result in deductions from, or complete cancellation of their direct payments.⁴⁹ Cross compliance also defines the reference level for voluntary agri-environment measures. In many cases, this implies adopting agricultural activities or levels of production intensity that deliver positive environmental outcomes, while not necessarily being the first choice from the point of view of profitability.⁵⁰ Among the many cross-compliance rules, Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition (GAEC) requires farmers to respect certain minimum standards for maintaining their land. These requirements are established by the Member States at national or regional level and cover the protection of soil against erosion, the maintenance of soil organic matter and soil structure, and the avoidance of the deterioration of habitats for wildlife.⁴⁸

The reform of the CAP for the period 2014-2020 introduced a new policy instrument of the first pillar (greening) directed to the provision of environmental public goods. This instrument has been designed to reward farmers for respecting three obligatory agricultural practices: (i) maintenance of permanent grassland; (ii) maintenance of ecological focus areas (land left fallow, terraces, landscape features, buffer strips and afforested areas), and (iii) crop diversification.⁵⁰ The reform also aimed to increase and strengthen the environmental component to Pillar 2, by including agri-environmental-climate measures, forestry measures and investments that are advantageous for the environment or climate (amongst others) in rural development strategies.⁵⁰ Agri-environmental measure provides the opportunity for farmers to participate in two schemes with the main aim of soil protection: conversion of arable land to grassland and growing cover crops. These schemes enable the state to compensate farmers for environmental services and thus act as an incentive.⁵¹ Since 2010, CAP reforms included support climate action. Indeed, the reformed CAP structure offers the possibility of including climate action instruments in both Pillar 1 and Pillar 2; however, in some cases the impact of such measures is still uncertain.⁵⁰ The CAP 2023-27 entered into force on January 2023 which marked the beginning of the implementation of the 28 approved CAP Strategic Plans in 27 EU countries.⁵² In the new CAP, payments will continue to be linked to a set of mandatory rules, i.e. "conditionality", comprising of statutory management requirements (SMR) and GAECs, but these rules will include a higher level of ambition.⁵³

The literature also refers to EU sectoral instruments which influence indirectly soil use. While the Nitrates Directive primarily targets water quality, it may have positive effects on local and diffuse

soil contamination, with side-effects on soil biodiversity. For example, when fertiliser spreading is banned in the winter period (with prevailing wet or water-saturated soils), soil compaction and water erosion (due to their interrelationship) might be positively affected.⁴⁷ Considering the strong connection between soil and water quality, directives on water quality may contribute to minimise erosion (in particular the Water Framework Directive) and spread soil contamination. Therefore, although it is unclear whether these Directives produce a reduction of soil organic carbon, those measures could be beneficial for soil biodiversity (Schils et al., 2008).⁴⁷ Since the Sewage Sludge Directive (86/278/EEC) specifies that it aims at establishing initial measures in connection with soil protection, it is considered to address the decline of organic matter, soil biodiversity and diffuse soil contamination.⁵⁴ Protection and conservation of soils are not mentioned explicitly in either the Birds or Habitats Directive. However, soil protection can be considered an implicit precondition for the protection or recovery of habitats.³¹ Moreover, the Habitats and Birds Directives may indirectly contribute to addressing a number of soil threats through the protection and restoration of semi-natural and natural habitats.⁵⁵

More recent literature examines legal and policy aspects of soil protection in the European Green Deal (EGD) and in its sub-strategies.³¹ In particular, the Farm to Fork Strategy promotes a transition towards fair, healthy and environment-friendly European food systems and is at the centre of the European Green Deal with regard to soil protection by targeting, more specifically, food insecurity, climate resilience, biodiversity and environmental protection in general.³¹ In this regard, the April 2021 Resolution of the European Parliament on soil protection, also acknowledged sustainable soil management as a "key component of farming and food policy in the long term".³¹ The European Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (COM/2020/380) also considers soils as a habitat in its own rights.²¹ Indeed, it tackles the key drivers of biodiversity loss, including unsustainable use of land, and acknowledges the role of soil organisms to "regulate and control key ecosystem services such as soil fertility, nutrient cycling and climate regulation" and thus takes up an important aspect of biological soil protection.³¹ Developing a proposal for binding EU nature restoration targets is a key element of the new biodiversity strategy. It focuses on soil biodiversity and encourages the maintenance of at least 10% of agricultural areas containing highly diverse landscape elements, such as buffer zones which have a high potential of soil organic carbon storage and sequestration as well as soil erosion and loss prevention, air and water filtering and resilience to climate change. This is intended to promote the transition to fully sustainable agricultural practices, as biodiversity conservation is crucial for food security and can bring direct economic benefits to many sectors.³¹ A comparative analysis of the different approaches adopted by EU Member States highlights the absence of a common EU strategy to address soil protection and the inefficacy of the subsidiary principle in the sustainable management of soil resources especially in the view of addressing the Sustainable Development Goals achieving the targets by 2030.⁵⁶ Indeed, in many countries, soils are seen as an issue limited to national sovereignty, because soils are always connected with concrete sites.⁵⁷ This has resulted in a complex system of strategies overall Europe for soil protection⁵⁶ and made the establishment of a global soil governance mechanisms difficult.⁵⁷

Moreover, many countries do not fill the "regulatory gap" regarding to soil. This means that many countries do not have a formal legal framework for soil protection.⁵⁸

Bone et al., 2010⁵⁹ show that the majority of EU member states legislation is focused on soil contamination. Netherlands, Germany and Belgium do have policies addressing broader soil protection issues and are the only states with a specific legally binding definition of soil.⁶⁰ The Netherlands have a number of policies to address long term protection, management and sustainable use of soils.⁶¹ The Soil Protection Act, in force since 1987, is the national framework for soil quality protection that aims to limit land use changes and regulates the application of waste, contaminated water or sludge in the soil.⁶² The Soil Quality Decree of 2008 aims to guarantee a balance between economic and social purposes with soil protection.⁶³ The Environment Protection Act is also one of the most important laws for soil protection. National Spatial Planning Programme are published approximately on a ten-year basis by the Ministry for Housing, Spatial Planning and the Environment.³²

Italy regulates soil protection mainly with four national acts: the Decree on Sewage Sludge of 1992,⁶⁴ the Decree on Regional Waste Management Plans of 2006⁶⁵, the Protocol of Soil Conservation of the Alpine Convention of 1998⁶⁶, the Legislative Decree on Orientation and Modernization of the Forestry Sector of 2001.⁶⁷ Above all, there is the Environmental Code of 2006 that sets the regulatory framework for any environmental issues including soil protection.⁶⁵ The National Strategy for Climate Change adaptation, adopted in 2015, includes the issue of soil degradation and desertification related to climate change, defining the measures of protection and the global warming mitigation with reference to UNFCCC.⁶⁸ The National Biodiversity Strategy, which came into force in 2010, is derived from the ratification of the UN Convention on Biological Diversity with law 124/94. The strategy includes specific measures for soil protection and restoration to guarantee sustainable agricultural practices and management of soil, forest and water. There is also the Italian landslides inventory devoted to data collection on landslides phenomena and two other decrees concerning soil protection.⁶⁹ Spain addresses the protection of soils from wind erosion and landslides/flooding mainly by instruments devoted to forests and their management such as the Forestry Law (no. 43/2003) that establishes the National framework for preventing forest fires, reducing land degradation and restoration of land.³²

In 2005, Croatia has adopted a national law aimed at managing natural areas where soil is mentioned as a crucial resource that must be protected from erosion by water and wind.⁷⁰ Lithuania adopted many national laws that directly address soil protection. Soil protection has been guaranteed by the Law on Environmental Impact Assessment since 1996 and updated in 2013 which directly addresses threats (contamination, loss of biodiversity, wind and water erosion, sealing) and provides mitigation measures for reducing impacts. The Regulations on Contaminated Sites Treatment Procedures also deals directly with soil protection.⁷¹ The Law on protected areas, in force since 1993, aims to preserve ecosystems and promote ecological farming.⁷² Lastly, the Law on forests to regulate reforestation, forest protection and forest use since 1994 also supports soil protection.⁷³ The water cycle regulation is also included in the national law.^{32,74}

2.1.2.3 Business innovation for soil health

Based on the soil degradation scale analysed in the previous section, this section explores the business innovation system for soil health at multiple level, which includes setting hard constraints, such as targets, forms of compensation, such as credits, and incentives, such as payments for ecosystem services.

At the international level, by adopting the SDGs, and in particular the Land Degradation Neutrality target in SDG 15.3, states agreed to strive to achieve a land degradation neutral (LDN) world by 2030. Although the LDN target needs indicators in order to be made operational the CCD claimed leadership for implementation of target 15.3 on LDN.⁷⁵ However, Keesstra et al., 2016 show that the UNCCD is only restricted to drylands. Moreover, the three conventions prescribed actions related to soil which include the development of national action plans and the definition of specific targets and indicators for the monitoring of natural resources at national level.⁴³ Fowler et al., 2019⁷⁶ argue that the LDN target in SDG 15.3 could be incorporated within an agreement like the Paris Agreement in order to become a binding goal.⁷⁵ As Subsection 2.1.4 showed, the Paris Agreement fails to explicitly refer to 'soil', 'land or 'agriculture'. However, Article 4 includes the target "to achieve a balance between anthropogenic emissions by sources and removals by sinks of GHGs in the second half of this century" which has implication on agricultural production.

Started from the need for measurable policy targets emerging in the framework of the UNCCD, Salvia et al., 2019 argues that the definition of target areas needing specific actions for biodiversity and landscape protection.^{77,78} The 1971 Ramsar Convention on 'Wetlands' current strategic plan links to the LDN target in SDG 15.3. The literature reveals that, although the Ramsar Convention with its mandate for wetlands and the CCD with its mandate for drylands are complementary, cooperation between the two is basic and could be improved.¹² Moreover, the Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring Law affirms that restoring, maintaining and enhancing soil health is a target in the new Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.⁷⁹

At EU level, the European Green Deal (EGD) targets, more or less directly, some aspects of soil protection. Actions and conservation measures under Targets 1,2,3 and 6 of the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2020 (COM (2011) 244) should contribute to limit soil compaction, acidification, contamination, loss of soil biodiversity, loss of soil organic matter, erosion and flooding.⁸⁰ The first European Climate Law includes an ambitious 2030 climate target of at least 55% reduction of net emissions of GHG as compared to 1990 and process for setting a 2040 climate target.³¹ The Farm to Fork Strategy includes ambitious and concrete targets to be achieved by 2030: a reduction of chemical and hazardous pesticides by 50%, a reduction of fertilizer use by 20%, a quota of 25% of EU arable land dedicated to organic farming and a reduction of sales of antimicrobials by 50%.³¹ Under the recent EU Soil Strategy, published in November 2021, which updates the Soil Thematic Strategy (COM/2021/699), the Commission announced that it will "limit land take by implementing ambitious national, regional and local targets by 2023" among the other objectives.²¹

Globally, while there is an increasing number of countries and companies setting climate neutrality goals, restoring and increasing natural carbon sinks is a mechanism to compensate for remaining

emissions. Pascual et al., 2015 explains that through the use of economic incentives, farmers manage soils as a carbon sink to benefit society at large.⁸¹ This is done as environmental schemes or as cross compliance regulation in the current two pillars of the EU CAP regulations. An alternative approach is a linked markets approach in which the provision of a public ecosystem service is linked to the provision of a private good. Eco-labelling schemes fall into this category (Kroeger and Casey, 2007).^{81,82} However, some scholars reflect on the fact that while this provides an opportunity to increase soil protection through the climate regime, there are also risks if soil protection is sought just from a climate perspective. Therefore, rules of gaining offsetting credits need to be strong in particular with regard to soil measures.¹²

As Subsection 2.1.4 explained, in the 2014-20 CAP, the environment is targeted through a combination of measures in both Pillar 1, through cross-compliance and green payments, and Pillar 2, mainly through voluntary measures with compensation for cost incurred and income forgone.⁸³ Under mandatory measures (e.g. cross compliance rules) farmers have to respect the reference level of soil quality at their own expense.⁴⁷ Prior to the 2003 reform, farmers received direct payments only if they produced particular commodities. After decoupling, agricultural sector moved more towards the free market and give farmers greater freedom to produce according to market demand. However, receipt of the income support payment is made on condition that farmers look after the farmland and fulfil environmental, animal welfare and food safety standards.⁴⁸ Although, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) provides subsidies for different management choices for land management, Pillar 1 is the CAP's priority, receiving >70% of the post-2020 budget and 94% of Pillar 1 consists of direct payments. Moreover, the majority of direct payments do not have specific provisions for environmentally friendly practices (including beneficial practices for soil biodiversity).²¹ Direct payments also have to consider the national CAP strategic plans, which will include environmental and climate objectives.²¹

In addition, farmers can choose to target a higher level of soil quality (target) under voluntary incentive-based measures (e.g. agri-environment payments). The related payments compensate for income losses due to reduced productivity or extra costs incurred when implementing the contract.⁴⁷ Kutter et al., 2011⁵⁶ highlight that soil quality was often reported as an expected side effect of voluntary incentive-based measures.⁵⁶ Prager et al., 2011 underline the necessary combination of mandatory and incentive tools among the others.⁸⁴ Braitto et al., 2020 explain that monetary incentives such as agri-environmental schemes (AES) do have the intended and primary effect of motivating behavioral change by offering financial rewards. However, long-term changes in soil management might be better promoted by adding other or supplementary measures, such as facilitating group learning.⁸⁵ Moreover, some farmers started to recognize the value of policy-induced soil management practices after implementing it. Thus, the participation in agri-environmental schemes induced a shift towards more environmentally friendly attitudes for some.⁸⁵ Awareness-raising measures also aim at promoting soil quality objectives, but their compliance is voluntary, and the programmes attempt to raise the awareness of farmers.⁴⁷ Prazan et al., 2011, as Slangen et al., 2008, point-out that a common reason for failure of incentive based

policy measures relates to the lack of trust which is so important for building long term contracts e.g. agri-environmental schemes.⁵¹ ⁸⁶The prevailing motivation for implementing soil conservation measures was the financial incentives provided by agri-environmental schemes and a fear of not complying with cross-compliance rules. In other words, voluntary provision was rather rare.⁵¹ Köninger et al., 2022 affirm that regulatory soil protection legislation should be coupled to incentive-based instruments such as direct payments of the CAP as Statutory Management Requirements, mandatory to receive direct payments. This would contribute to a "greener" design of the CAP which has been heavily questioned in the literature.²¹

Although approaches such as Payments For Ecosystem Services (PES) might be more effective in promoting sustainable land management than the standard 'polluter pays' principle,^{87,88} the literature recognise that instituting PES schemes to compensate for the safeguarded ecosystem services can be highly challenging for many land covers and uses. This is because the available methods to measure the types, flows and values of ecosystem services under different land covers and uses remain highly reduced.⁸⁷ Differently, the implementation of a different approach to soil policy and farm subsidies based on a "Payment for Practice" rather than attempting to find a soil health indicator that will do all things for all people would concurrently provide evidence to policy makers on which to form policy while providing robust guidelines for farmers and land managers.⁸⁹ Moreover, while in Western countries soil conservation measures are often financially supported by the state (through so called "payments for ecosystem services"), in other regions of the world, for example in China, the contributions of the private sector and those who benefit directly from soil protection are much higher (Xin et al., 2012).^{17,90}

In Italy, show that actual profitability proved to be the main effective stimulus to the adoption of Soil Conservation Practices, much more than the ecological attitude of farmers or the presence of subsidies.⁹¹ Di Bene et al., 2022 highlight that rural development programmes (RDPS) have provided payments per hectare of agricultural area as financial support the adoption of crop diversification strategies and the renewal of the machinery and tools.³⁴ In Spain, Marques et al., 2015 show that despite the proven convenience of European grants, SLM practices remain uncommon.⁹² Poland mixes mandatory instruments with incentives to promote sets of management practices linked with sustainable soil management, although the relevance of soil health is not completely recognised.⁹³ Lahmar R., 2010 shows that in Norway and Germany the adoption of conservation agriculture has been encouraged and subsidised in order to mitigate soil erosion.⁹⁴ In the Flemish region, cross-compliance is only implemented in some areas and only for a limited period of time to force farmers in the most erosion vulnerable areas to take action and implement the required management practices. These practices are mandatory for these farmers and no compensations, but reductions in direct payments are provided as fines in these cases. In the other areas that are less erosion vulnerable, only voluntary participation of the farmers is encouraged through subsidies.⁹⁵ Prosperi et al., 2011 explain that French farmers who are not under the Single Payment Scheme (such as those in viticulture or horticulture) but subscribe to voluntary agri-environmental

measures are also subject to cross-compliance rules. At the French level, the national decree 'Zones under environmental constraints' (ZUNC) (Decree No. 2007/882) offers an incentive-based action programme for farmers who voluntarily decide to adopt measures for the protection of humid areas with a high potential for biodiversity, 'drinking water' and erosion areas identified by Prefects following the recommendations of local committees on the environment, health risk, agriculture and water.⁹⁶

2.1.3 Conclusions

As the literature review showed, soil health is embedded in different sectoral policy and legal instruments at multiple levels. In other words, the review reveals a lack of a comprehensive protection of soil health due to a fragmentation of policy, legislation and economic instruments related to soil. However, the importance of soil health has been recognised at global level and the EU has made commitments in the international context of the three Rio Conventions. The Union is also committed to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which healthy soils contribute directly to.

International environmental policy is far from achieving comprehensive soil protection. There exists no specific soil convention yet, but binding instruments in other fields of environmental policy might influence the use of the soils. Especially, the UNCCD is the only international treaty specifically addressing land-related issues, while the definition of desertification therein clearly relates to soil conservation. The Union and its Member States, as Parties to the UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), approved by Council Decision 98/216/EC, have committed to combat desertification and mitigate the effects of drought in affected countries. However, certain overlaps with the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in terms of legal scope and mandate regarding soil biodiversity may occur, as the diversity within species and ecosystems is closely linked and reliant upon the conservation of soils and ecosystems. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) also creates obligations that reduce climate change thus reducing the threat of soil degradation. Soil as well as land use, land degradation and sustainable land management are closely linked to climate change in terms of carbon capture and storage and the emissions from deforestation and agriculture, as underlined by Article 4 of the PA. However, the PA only indirectly addresses soil protection in the general context of climate change. However, among the 17 SDGs of the United Nations, especially SDG 15 refers to soil-related threats (biodiversity, desertification, deforestation) and presents specific targets that require a legislative intervention.

Although current EU and national policies have made positive contributions to improving soil health, they do not tackle all the drivers of soil degradation and therefore significant gaps remain. The Sewage Sludge Directive (Directive 86/278/EEC, OJ 1986 L 181, p. 6 ff; OJ 1991 L 377, p. 48 ff.) of 1986 forms the first legal instrument partly contributing to the protection of soils. However, where an instrument has direct implications on certain aspects of soil protection, it does not set any specific soil-related requirements. Indeed, while Soil Sealing Guidelines [SWD (2012) 101] does not

have explicit soil-focused objectives, it involves the use of soil management measures to reach its aim, such as the use of cover crops or crop rotations. As one of the main areas of EU legislation relating to soils, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) introduced measures directly linked to soil protection as subsidies measures (eco-schemes and AECMs) and specify pre-conditions of eligibility for area-based subsidies (GAECs). However, the implementation of beneficial conservation activities within the CAP depends on various decision levels.

While the Biodiversity Strategy explicitly addresses land degradation and restoration of soil (protected areas +30%, aiming to plant more than 3 billion trees by 2030), there is currently no uniform definition of soil biodiversity protection at the EU level. Also, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 does not address the risks associated with soil compaction and conventional tillage. Since soil biodiversity sustains above-ground life, the EU has recently announced its new Soil Strategy to better protect soil ecosystems as part of the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

As part of the European Green Deal, the Commission adopted an EU Soil Strategy for 2030 which sets out the long-term vision to have all soils in healthy condition by 2050, to make protection, sustainable use and restoration of soils the norm and proposes a combination of voluntary and legislative actions to achieve these aims. The new EU Soil Strategy for 2030 announced legal instruments in certain areas of action and a legislative proposal on soil health by 2023. Indeed, a Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law) was realised on 5 July 2023. Article 1 sets out the overarching objective of the directive which is to put in place a coherent soil monitoring framework that will provide data on soil health in all Member States and to ensure that EU soils are in healthy condition by 2050 at the latest, so that they can supply multiple services at a scale sufficient to meet environmental, societal and economic needs and to reduce soil pollution to levels no longer considered harmful to human health. This will also help to implement SG15, its Target 15.3 on land degradation neutrality and the other soil-relevant SDGs, to meet the requirements of the PA and to secure healthy food for future generations as well.

2.2 Mapping Financial and Economic Instruments

2.2.1 Methods

The review of the scientific literature relating to the economic-financial instruments applied to the context of healthy soil was conducted starting from the definition of a research protocol. In particular, the framework was outlined according to the logic, objective and methodology useful for reviewing the current state of the art of economic and financial instruments that promote and assist the development of healthy soil. The protocol structure was developed based on the recommendations provided by Peters et al. (2020)⁹⁷, Tricco et al. (2018)⁹⁸. The main elements and the research method applied to the review will be briefly presented below.

The study considered peer reviewed, journal articles, books and their chapters. English language publications in a time range between 1990 and 2023 were included.

Two bibliographic databases, Scopus and Web of Science, were used to search the bibliography with the aim of maximizing the result and coverage of publications.¹ The keyword string was created to include all financial instruments and economic incentives studied in relation to the issue of healthy soil, its conservation and preservation. A set of financial instruments were selected from the BIOFIN catalogue in order to compose the search string including the part of keywords related to soil, "soil protection" OR "soil restoration" OR "soil rehabilitation" OR "soil conservation", with the part of keywords related to financial solutions, "impact bond" OR "payments for ecosystem service*" OR "PES" OR "fund*" OR "cost benefit" OR "credit*" OR "debit*" OR "market based" OR "market*" OR "incentive*" OR "environmental charge*" OR "tax" OR "payment" OR "compensation" OR "easement" OR "fiscal transfer" OR "subside*" OR "fees" OR "sustainability standard*" OR "certification*" OR "cost effectiveness" OR "eco label*" OR "financial guarantee*" OR "public guarantee*" OR "private guarantee*".

During the title screening phase, an online software, Hubmeta, was used, which allowed the review team to analyse more than 4000 titles and abstracts based on a review criteria scheme previously defined by the entire team. The articles resulting from this phase constituted the body of literature that was analysed in detail in the full text screening phase. In this phase, an attribute matrix was defined that ensured the extrapolation of data useful for the composition of the catalogue. The research team reviewed a total of 235 scientific articles, catalogued according to the methodological framework described in the protocol. The result of the full text review produced a total of 101 articles, which were identified as relevant for the purpose of our analysis. Consequently, a more specific attribute extraction matrix was defined, and the review team further selected the articles to the number of 92 papers.

2.2.2 Results

A total of 92 articles was analysed and they were selected from the literature review according to the analysis protocol presented as an annex to this Report.

The construction of the analysis matrix allowed to extrapolate the information necessary to map the financial instruments applied to the issue of healthy soil. In particular, three main dimensions of analysis were defined. A first set of attributes helped to identify the references of scientific articles in order to better understand the spatial distribution of research across continents and the distribution over the years.

Empirical research activity on economic instruments in the context of healthy soil issues has increased since its first appearance in 1990. Graph 1 shows that over the last 16 years, more than $\frac{3}{4}$ of all articles examined in the entire 33-year period (1990-2023) have been published. The highest peak is registered in the two five-year periods 2011-2015 and 2016-2020. The geographic distribution

¹ The search was performed in October 2023.

of research shows that the majority of studies concern Asia (22.3%) followed by Europe (20.2%) and North America (14.9%).

Graph 1 The total distribution of papers among decades and continents.

The second set of attributes was constructed with the aim of identifying the soil pressures in detail. On the basis of these, funded instruments acting in different sectors such as agricultural, urban, forestry, watershed and generic, and with respect to different issues concerning soil services, soil functions and soil properties,⁹⁹ were categorised. Figure 1 shows the methodological scheme applied to this part of the analysis.

Figure 1 Methodological scheme applied to soil.

Finally, the third set of attributes was defined in order to capture the constituent elements of the different financial instruments analysed. A financial solution is an integrated approach to solve a specific problem or challenge through the use of financial and economic instruments. It is based on a combination of elements including one or more financial instruments, sources of financing, main beneficiaries or stakeholders and the desired financial outcome or result.¹⁰⁰ Figure 2 shows the methodological framework applied to this phase, revised by the authors from that used in the BIOFIN catalogue.

Figure 2 Methodological scheme applied to financial solutions.

The lack of a common theoretical and empirical framework makes the study and analysis of active financial solutions difficult to be implemented in the future. As pointed out by Pirard and Lapeyre (2014), the common trait with respect to scientific literature and theory seems to be that nature has a price, or rather the preservation, conservation and restoration of nature have a price.¹⁰¹

Therefore, a classification of instruments was developed based on their economic characteristics. The main distinction exists between price-based instruments, which set a price on environmental goods to create incentives, and quantity-based instruments, which define a level of use of environmental goods to create incentives.¹⁰²

The classification applied to this research, uses the two sets mentioned above, and, given the cross-cutting nature of the issue of healthy soil, it complements the classification with three additional categories: Insurance-related instruments, Investment/disinvestment instruments and Regulatory instruments. This subdivision was made at the same time as the literature review with the main aim of facilitating the understanding and utilisation of the results by stakeholders and project partners. Table 1 shows the methodological and applicative framework, with the definition

of the 5 categories where the different financial instruments and economic incentives are classified according to the definition given by BIOFIN.

Category	Instrument	Definition
Price based instruments	Grant	An instrument that encompasses transfers made in cash, goods or services for which no repayment is expected. The definition includes ODA. Individual donations also take the form of grants.
	Fiscal	Any instrument involving a fiscal reform and a subsequent change in the tax code, subsidies or fiscal allocation formula. Fiscal measures include both revenue-generating activities such as the establishment of a green tax and the phasing out of harmful public subsidies.
Quantity based instruments	Market	Any instrument that involves or directly influences market transactions or prices. Markets match the supply and demand of a product or service. Markets can be created by public regulations such as cap-and-trade carbon markets.
Investment/ disinvestment instruments	Debt/Equity	An obligation to make a payment or the acquisition of ownership rights (company or financial asset) in exchange of a payment. Debt can be in the form of repayable loans, government or corporate bonds, etc. Equity can be company stock or other forms of ownership and is often a riskier investment than debt.
Insurance related instruments	Risk management	Any instrument that involves the transfer of risks between two or more parties. The transfer of risks can be attached to a payment transaction (e.g. a typical insurance scheme) or a specific agreement (contract) between two or more parties.
Regulatory instruments	Regulatory	Any instrument or approach involving a regulatory reform such as a change in laws, policies, regulations, and/or enforcement.

Table 1 Category categories defined for the methodological framework applied to financial and economic instruments.

The other analysis attributes, shown in Figure 2, refer to the source of finance (Public, Private or in the form of a Public-Private combination); the results that the financial instrument helps to achieve (Avoid future expenditures, Deliver better, Generate revenues and Realign expenditures); and finally the beneficiaries of the instrument or economic incentive (the Land users, Individuals and Organisations).

In particular, the research incorporated the comprehensive framework for biodiversity finance built around four key desired outcomes promoted by BIOFIN. These four complementary outcomes recognise that all strategies, instruments and financing operate within complex systems. By specifying these four outcomes as a lens for identifying and prioritising financial solutions,

stakeholders can seek a mix of comprehensive, innovative and effective financial solutions. Table 2 shows the description for each outcome.

Finance Results	Definition
Avoid future expenditures	Measures that can prevent or reduce the need to undertake a future investment. This means eliminating or amending existing counter-productive policies and expenditures (e.g. increasing taxes on sugar content or tobacco), investing in preventative actions and infrastructure (green infrastructure, prevention of invasive alien species), or aligning business and livelihood practices with sustainable development. Examples include taxes on harmful products (this can generate a double dividend) or strong fines for illegal introduction of alien species.
Deliver better	Measures that can enhance cost-effectiveness and efficiency in budget execution, achieve synergies, align incentives, and favour a more equitable distribution of resources. Examples include the establishment of biodiversity business challenge funds, the merger or coordination of national conservation funds or donor efforts, retention of park entrance fees to better motivate managers, and the establishment of central procurement units or staff incentives to increase delivery of resources.
Generate revenues	Measures that can generate or leverage financial resources allocated to biodiversity. Examples include protected area user fees, the attraction of impact investment in conservation projects, the revision or introduction of green taxes (fuel taxes, taxes on chemical pesticides, water fees, etc.), the issuance of debt instruments such as green and blue bonds, etc.
Realign expenditures	Measures that reorient existing financial flows towards improved biodiversity management. Main options include reducing, redirecting or eliminating subsidies and other spending that harms biodiversity and increasing or redirecting financial flows towards biodiversity. Another example is lobbying for shifting budget allocations towards biodiversity.

Table 2 Definition of Finance Results. Source BIOFIN

As the previous paragraphs introduced, in order to provide a systematic overview of the research, the papers were categorised according to the dimensions defined for soil and financial solutions. These dimensions were identified inductively on the basis of the topics discussed in the papers. Figure 3 summarises the results of the dimensions concerning the methods, the soil sector, the soil pressures, and the financial category.

The analysis carried out by the researchers was divided in 50.5% of the cases into analysis and in-depth analysis of the actual case of the application of the financial solution to a specific context (Realistic), while in 49.5% of the papers analysed, the research focused on the study of scenarios and ex-ante evaluations (Hypothetic).

Figure 3 Summary of Methods, Soil Sector, Soil Pressure and Financial Instrument Category dimensions.

Regarding the methodological approach applied by researchers to investigate financial solutions applied to soil (Figure 3, top left), for 53.8% the dominant approach is quantitative. The set of quantitative methods is composed of econometric analyses, cost-benefit analyses, simulations, statistical analyses, economic models coupled with land-use models, regression models and agent-based models. While qualitative approaches present 24.7%, they involve survey methods with the application of questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, evaluation methods, literature and documentation analysis and field visits. Mixed methods are applied to 21.5% of analyses and present the use of mixed approaches that integrate qualitative data such as interviews and questionnaires with quantitative data such as spatial data or econometric models.

Regarding the dimension referring to the type of soil sector (Figure 3, top right), when talking about soil, five categories were defined: agriculture, forests, urban, watershed and general. The most investigated sector is agriculture, followed by watershed and forestry. Few studies deal with urban soil issues, in particular analyzing the land use decisions in urban areas,¹⁰³ and estimating the costs and benefits of soil conservation practices.¹⁰⁴ Many papers analysed several sectors together, by combining the agricultural, forestry and watershed sectors. Included within the generic sector are studies that deal with analysing the general soil context without specifying the relevant sector,¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁹ studies that focus on soil in relation to mining.¹¹⁰

With regard to the dimension related to the soil pressures (Figure 3, bottom left) categories were created that could capture the heterogeneity of the studies and at the same time categories that could summarise common features. As shown in Figure 1, a number of soil constraints have been defined as major issues representing the concept of healthy soil in parts. Soil health and soil quality are considered synonymous and can be used interchangeably. Soil health invokes the idea that soil is an ecosystem full of life that needs to be carefully managed to regain and maintain our soil's ability to function optimally.⁹⁹ This is why soil pressures have been categorised within categories referring to the different problems investigated by researchers and for which the applied financial solutions seek to remedy. Within the category of soil services, which accounts for 9.7% of the papers, the following constraints are included: organic matter decline, biodiversity loss and critical watershed. In the category of soil properties, with 23.7% of the contributions from studies and research, the following constraints are included: compaction, unsustainable land use and degradation; the category of soil functions is in the majority with 34.4% of the researches having dealt with issues concerning: desertification, erosion, salinization, contamination and eutrophication. Finally, there is the mix category, which groups several constraints that relate to different categories and accounts for 32.3% of the literature review. This aspect highlights how the research investigates the application of the financial solution by expanding the concept of healthy soil in a cross-cutting and comprehensive manner.

Regarding the dimension related to the category of financial instruments (Figure 3, bottom right), price-based instruments are the most analysed type of instruments. Within them, we have catalogued research that analyses subsidies, PES, economic incentives, grants and in general all those financial and economic solutions that base their operation on price. Regulatory instruments are the second largest category, within which instruments involving regulatory reform, such as changes in laws, policies, regulations and/or enforcement, are included. Debt instruments that may take the form of repayable loans, government or corporate bonds have been investigated in the minority. Finally, instruments based on quantity and those referring to risk transfer have been little investigated.

The results of the literature review will be presented in the following Sections following the five classification categories.²

2.2.2.1 Price-based instruments

Price-based instruments impose prices on environmental goods and services to account for their value in existing markets. They change the structure of individual costs and benefits and consequent land patterns and prices.¹¹¹

² *It must be borne in mind that most of the financial solutions analysed present a mix of characters and that therefore the main purpose of the classification is to present the catalogue of instruments in a coherent and comprehensive manner.*

The set of price-based instruments includes Grant, Fiscal and Market instruments. Figure 4 summarises some attributes and characteristics of price-based financial instruments and solutions. The majority scale of investigation is the regional and local scale. Much research focuses on the operation or implementation of the instrument at the watershed scale, in the rural context of a region or municipality, or the space of a protected area or forest. The majority of beneficiaries are land users, farmers who use and act on the land and towards whom the financial instruments seek to influence land use practices. This last data is consistent with the indication that the majority of financial solutions are of public origin (79.7%). Most policy instruments are multi-dimensional as public policies seem to combine rather than choose among different approaches.¹⁰¹ Any given instrument can have many characteristics that simultaneously refer to regulation, free market exchanges, negotiations, distribution of monetary rewards and are mainly aimed at direct and primary users of land, land users. With respect to results, the majority of instruments promote cost-effectiveness and cost-efficiency and direct their action towards compensating potential losses resulting from the implementation of soil conservation and restorative practices (deliver better, 49.4%). As noticed before, policies combine several strategies together, e.g. with the aim of avoiding future expenditures (26.5%), co-developing measures to control erosion and contamination and to avoid the loss of fertile land, or the preservation of watersheds.

This report classifies price-based instruments according to specific type of soil pressures, i.e. soil functions, soil services, soil properties and mix category.

Figure 4 The Scale, Beneficiaries, Source and Results attributes of Financial Instruments.

The mapping of financing solutions highlights how 40.6% of the price-based instruments concern pressures affecting soil functions, such as desertification, erosion, salinization, contamination and eutrophication. Barbier (1990) investigates the incentives for upland farmers on Java to adopt soil conservation packages as a means to control erosion.¹¹² The evidence demonstrates that without appropriate economic incentives, such as subsidies for conservation practices, and long-term credit loans, upland farmers will not modify their land management practices and farming systems. Bizer (2005) analyses factors that affect soil functions by the decisions and alternative choices available in Northrhine-Wesfalia state, in Germany.¹¹³ The results obtained through the application of a behavioral model show the validity of the option of implementing the special land use tax as a reform model for existing property taxes. This land use tax applies different rates depending on the ecological damage. As a result, areas covered by buildings will pay higher tax rates than vacant space. Conventional agriculture will pay more than forest areas and nature reserve areas will be free. The author also notes that such a land use tax, designed as a revenue-neutral alternative to the German property tax, could trigger modest changes in land use behavior in the near future. Feng et al. (2006) investigate how the existence of a fixed budget allocation among programs affects the amounts of environmental benefits achievable under alternative policy implementation schemes, such as erosion reduction and carbon sequestration.¹¹⁴ The conceptual framework is applied to an agricultural region of North America, using field-scale data along with empirical models, and a biophysical process simulation model for a variety of environmental benefits. The results show that conservation practices are more cost-effective than the option of conservation through set-aside. The authors also find that large efficiency losses may occur due to the pre-establishment of conservation budgets, regardless of whether a simultaneous or sequential implementation strategy is followed. The question of the reference value for determining payments for conservation practices also remains controversial. Hosseini et al. (2008) measure the effects of soil conservation practices on soil quality in dry-farmed wheat in Iran (Zanjan province) by using a bioeconomic production function.¹¹⁵ The results show that the effect of non-mechanical soil conservation practices is 72% higher than alternative practices without soil conservation. The average gain from conservation (i.e., \$29.9 2008 ha) is sufficient to encourage extension, payment of green subsidies and investment in new conservation technologies. The authors conclude that implementing soil conservation practices would increase the real value of land and the well-being of farmers. Jack et al. (2009) describe how a payment contract auction can be designed to obtain the minimum acceptable payment as information during the design phase of a payment retention program, in the case study of the island of Sumatra where coffee farmers bid for payment contracts to implement erosion control.¹¹⁶ This information can then be used to generate an estimate of the ecosystem service supply curve for the program's target population. The results show that knowledge of the shape of the supply curve allows for facilitated modelling of the cost of the large-scale payment program, and the latter is useful in designing contracts and exploring trade-offs between poverty reduction and ecosystem service provision.. Spaan et al. (2010) investigate the evolution of the application of voluntary erosion control measures (Farm Erosion Management

Plan-FEMP) and credits developed for CAP payments, in Southern Limburg, the Netherlands.¹¹⁷ The FEMP together with CAP payments, gave the farmers the option to draw up a custom-made strategy for their farm, with emphasis on erosion control on critical locations. Field observations showed that the average protection of the farm was sufficient, but on field level the needed protection was not always sufficient. Extra measures at sensitive locations were not often taken. The analysis shows how, from the calculation of FEMP applications and the total area intended for erosion protection, there has been a progressive decline over time. Ban et al. (2013) develop an integrated governance model to manage nonpoint source (NPS) pollutions in watershed management practiced in Korea.¹¹⁸ The results indicate that the use of financial resources based on principles such as "polluter pays", "recipient pays" and "general tax source" are necessary governance-based NPS pollution management measures. Kauffman et al. (2014) highlight the need to make progress towards implementation of the Green Water Credits (GWC) program to organize payments from downstream businesses to upstream farmers. The study by Zolin et al. (2014) evaluates the effectiveness of the policies adopted in the Conservador das Aguas project in the Posses sub-basin (Brazil), which proved decisive in reducing erosion in the Posses sub-basin, given that its operation sees the payment of compensation not only with respect to the conserved area but compared to the total surface area of the property.¹¹⁹ Morri et al (2014) precisely identify who should pay for the forest ecosystem service from which they benefit in the context of the Apennines (Italy).¹²⁰ The results show that the value of soil protection has an inherent difficulty in defining the possible demand for services that are rarely considered and paid for by lay people (e.g. soil stability). Soil protection can only be perceived by specific land users (i.e. farmers) when this service is absent. Furthermore, the results show that indirect utilisation values of ecosystem services such as soil protection were three times higher than direct utilisation values (e.g. firewood production). Quang et al. (2004) identify the economic constraints to the adoption of sustainable practices and evaluate the level of monetary incentive that would be necessary to achieve a substantial reduction in erosion rates in Vietnam.¹²¹ Through simulations, researchers show reduced expansions of the areas subjected to soil conservation. Therefore payments are needed to encourage farmers to conserve soil, such as payment programs for ecosystem services PES. Gonzalez-Sanchez et al. (2015) evaluate the European funding program and National Rural Development Program to support conservation agriculture practices in Spain.¹²² The researchers argue that national and supranational funds have contributed to conservation agriculture (CA) practices, increasing the benefits for achieving the objectives established in the Kyoto Protocol. Makarov et al. (2016) develop an approach to the cadastral evaluation of land contaminated by radionuclides and used in agriculture and forestry.¹⁰⁵ The approach would allow the inclusion of contaminated land in the land tax system, as well as including the responsibility of the owners in the form of an additional ecological tax (payment compensation) aimed at maintaining the land in a normal state. Pande et al. (2017) assess the economic feasibility of bamboo planting and its role as an enabler of soil conservation measures, with implications for the reclamation of degraded lands in ravine ecologies in India.¹²³ Government programs that include subsidies and financial

assistance are cited as essential for the encouragement of such practices. Saad et al. (2018) examine how different restoration strategies could be reflected in soil conservation and sediment retention, in the Posses River, southeast Brazil, where one of the first Brazilian Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) projects is active.¹²⁴ In particular, the researchers calculate the PES contribution (applied to forest conservation, as a payment to farmers for maintaining forests instead of grazing) which is obtained as a benefit in terms of reduced restoration in a soil loss scenario. Monteiro et al. (2018) developed a methodology for PES that follows the basic principles of the land use capacity classification system proposed by the US Department of Agriculture.¹²⁵ The proposed methodology considers land use planning as an indispensable step in ensuring that the productive capacity of agricultural land is maintained to meet the growing global demand for food and agricultural inputs. The researchers identify some obstacles to the adoption of the proposed PES methodology, such as: the lack of financial resources for payment; payment values that are not attractive to landowners; a lack of awareness on the part of landowners that conservation practices can increase land productivity; the need for trained technical personnel to carry out and implement program management and monitoring; and specific reasons that discourage landowner interest or ability to conserve their property. Sone et al. (2019) evaluate the effectiveness of PES program in achieving the initial goals of reducing soil erosion and water production in an environmentally protected area, the Guaririba River Basin in west-central Brazil.¹²⁶ PES are in the form of funds to farmers that contribute to increasing water infiltration into the soil, decreasing soil loss and preserving biodiversity through conservation management practices. Results show that soil conservation practices increase base flow and decrease direct runoff in a short period of time. In addition, water companies can benefit from PES programs by reimbursing investments made. Prasuhn (2020) shows that the Swiss agricultural policy system is based on a complex system of direct payments (subsidies).¹²⁷ The National Ordinance on Direct Payments contains a clause according to which farmers who wish to receive direct payments must take appropriate measures to protect against soil erosion, for example by defining a minimum crop rotation or optimal soil cover. Furthermore, there are various cantonal and state programs to support conservation tillage. The soil support program, which was launched in the Canton of Bern and in the municipalities of the Frienisberg region, is based on voluntary participation and allows financial incentives for the implementation of various measures relating to cropping systems that protect the soil (mulching, strip inclined machining or no machining). The author highlights that not only financial incentives, but also extension service, training, awareness raising, exchange with colleagues and field inspections through a farmer-farmer approach, are crucial factors for the adoption of adequate measures. Biffi et al. (2021) develop an approach to compare subsidy systems across continents using an interdisciplinary human-environment systems perspective.¹²⁸ By using linear mixed models and linear models, the authors explored associations between AES agri-environmental scheme allocation and predictors at different scales. The results show that higher spending on AES is associated with areas of low soil organic carbon and high greenhouse gas emissions in both the US and the EU, and with a nitrogen

surplus in the EU. More than successes, however, clear misalignments between funding and environmental needs have emerged: AES allocation has not successfully targeted areas of greatest water stress, biodiversity loss, soil erosion and nutrient runoff. Socioeconomic and agricultural context variables may explain some of these misalignments. Such as AESs that have been allocated to areas with higher percentages of women producers in the EU but not in the US, where funds have been directed towards areas with fewer tenant farmers. Pathak et al. (2021) explains that the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) provides technical and financial support to farmers, private landowners, and managers to adopt agricultural conservation practices voluntarily in Louisiana, USA.¹²⁹ These conservation practices are known as best management practices (BMPs) and those are adopted to improve soil health and reduce nonpoint source pollution emanating from agricultural land. The results show that the effect of the federal conservation support fund is that the Environmental Quality Incentive Program (EQIP) and Conservation Stewardship Program (CSP) participants adopted about four more conservation practices than farmers with similar characteristics who were not participating in the program. Use of precision farming technology and integrated farming have also positive effect on the number of conservation practices adopted. Fowler et al. (2022) show how historical and voluntary efforts to reduce erosion achieve marginal returns in the arid interior Pacific Northwest of the United States.¹³⁰ The researchers point out that all the critical source areas (CSA) targets reduce erosion rates over the long term and that the most effective use of conservation funds occurs when the diffusion of the innovation mechanism is enhanced by large-scale payments for tillage reduction.

Price-based instruments dealing with pressures and referring to soil services, account for 6.3% and specifically address issues related to biodiversity loss, organic matter decline and critical watershed. Montagnini et al. (2005) analyze the Payment for Environmental Services (PES) that provides subsidies to farmers for plantations and agroforestry systems from a special tax on gasoline and from external sources sought by FONAFIFO (National Forest Financing Fund), in Costa Rica.¹³¹ The findings show that government incentives or other methods are needed to promote reforestation of degraded lands. Ruiz-Jiménez and Valtierra-Pacheco (2017) explains that the Program Environmental Hydrological Services (PSAH) of the National Authority Forestry Commission (CONAFOR) from 2005 to 2010, in Mexico,¹³² supported the ejido forest properties mainly by transferring economic resources in exchange for two main conditions: not carrying out forest extraction on the benefited properties and carrying out conservation work and tasks to improve the ecological conditions of the properties to be maintained the vegetal cover. The results show that PSAH-beneficiary properties are in better condition today than at the beginning of the program, and that the properties therefore adequately meet the provision of environmental hydrological services. Puspitasari et al. (2021) show how PES in watershed management is the implementation of a market mechanism to compensate upstream landowners for maintaining or modifying certain land uses that may affect the availability and/or quality of downstream water resources.¹³³ The PES mechanism, in these terms, has the ability to connect upstream and downstream interests, therefore it will involve different parties for its implementation. Important

factors include the context, which is mainly based on the basis and objectives of PES implementation, the actors involved in the PES scheme, the financing systems, the operations and the evaluation of PES monitoring. Finally, the analysis results show that there are important PES factors that need to be the focus of attention, including context (local regulation), actors (public understanding of PES mechanism), operation (PES planning design) and the community approach. lack of willingness to pay. The study conducted by Lin et al. (2023) propose a coupled ABM incentive policy evaluation tool to systematically compare the effectiveness of different incentive policies, including business as usual (BAU), pay-by-performance PFP on an individual basis and group-based PFP at scale of pelvis.¹³⁴ The results show that Pay-for-performance policies outperform the pay-for-practice policy in the simulation, achieving faster sediment reduction. Due to policy-induced collaboration, the group-based pay-for-performance policy shows reduced sensitivity to bonus payments.

Pressures on soil properties and related financial solutions were investigated by 20,3%, particularly unsustainable land use, degradation and compaction.

Grepperud (2000) analyses the preferences of farmers operating in an uncertain environment with respect to the influence that risk has on their optimal land conservation decisions in the absence of effective insurance markets.¹³⁵ The presence of risk preferences was found to improve incentives for soil conservation in a low-input farming system, regardless of the source of income risk considered. Herrador and Dimas (2000) analyse incentives in El Salvador to combat land degradation and at the same time to encourage sustainable practices among farmers, such as water conservation practices and agroforestry systems, with a focus on those financial solutions that generate a short-term profit and thus appear as a viable option for farmers.¹³⁶ The authors investigate ways to attribute value to at least some of the environmental and social benefits that were previously not recognised by the market through the implementation of PES schemes. Ananda and Herath (2001) examine the effects of pricing and subsidy policy on the adoption of soil conservation measures in tea lands in Sri Lanka.¹³⁷ The study uses a non-linear yield damage function to estimate the loss of tea yield due to soil erosion. The yield function is then used in conjunction with a simple analytical model to examine the effects of changes in prices and subsidies on incentives to adopt various soil conservation technologies, such as lateral drainage, stone terracing and farmland techniques, sloping agricultural land technology (SALT). The results show that soil conservation technologies are unlikely to be adopted in the region without a substantial increase in yield and that higher commodity prices encourage soil conservation. The researchers conclude by asserting that without positive yield increases, soil conservation is not economical at current prices. Hoogeveen and Oostendorp (2003) explain that in the absence of credit markets the response of households to exogenous price changes in land prices and agricultural production may differ from the predictions of cost-benefit analysis.¹³⁸ Differently, where increases in land prices and agricultural production are accompanied by the introduction of a credit market, the reactions of agricultural households are in line with the predictions made by the cost-benefit analysis. Winters et al. (2004) investigate possible alternatives to incentives, such

as the provision of conservation technologies combined with measures that promote short-term profit in the agricultural sector in the Andes, Ecuador.¹³⁹ The results of empirical case studies show that such measures succeed in influencing the long-term sustainable behaviour of farmers. Looking at economic incentives, a percentage of withdrawals were found once the incentive ended. Differently, considering measures that promote conservation technologies in combination with measures that improve short-term profitability, an increase in participation in the program is confirmed, which consequently increases the intensity of the adoption of conservation practices. Zabala et al. (2017) connected the theory of incentive-based conservation programs to promote the diffusion of pro-environmental behavior, with a case of a scheme to encourage silvo-pasture adoption in a small community in Chiapas, Mexico.¹⁴⁰ The research findings suggest that incentives other than payments may be more appropriate for those more likely to adopt silvo-pastoral practices, and that payments could encourage rent-seeking strategies and not necessarily promote permanent behavioral change. The study by Wang et al. (2019) examine that in the northern Great Plains of the United States, the Environmental Quality Incentives Program (EQIP) aims to improve agricultural land processing by providing up to 50% cost-sharing for many conservation practices.¹⁴¹ The researchers conclude by confirming that cost-sharing programs play an important role in removing financial barriers and promoting the widespread adoption of conservation tillage. Do et al. (2020) explains that agroforestry systems generate substantial profits in the long run, but also entail high establishment and maintenance costs and may generate net losses in the first few years.¹⁴² Therefore, initial financial incentives to compensate for these losses help to promote the adoption of agroforestry in the region. Penailillo et al. (2022) indicate that levels of potential soil erosion are not statistically different between SIRSD-S (Incentive System for the Agri-environmental Sustainability of Agricultural Soils) beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers in Chile.¹⁴³ In any case, the spatial analysis methodology applied to the case study represents a useful mechanism for policy makers to establish new criteria based on erosion, land use capacity and homogeneous areas, which would allow practices to be encouraged or discouraged based on observed levels of erosion. Brasil et al. (2023) indicate that implementing fallow practices in cattle ranching as a policy measure could reduce deforestation rates while simultaneously ensuring sustainable long-term agricultural productivity, thus diminishing the necessity to clear new forest land.¹⁴⁴ Moreover, when combined with payments for avoided deforestation, such as REDD+ carbon offsets, the opportunity costs associated with ranching land can be utilized to compensate for the loss of gross income resulting from the policy. Mucida et al. (2023) highlight how payment for environmental services can increase the environmental performance of agriculture, livestock and forestry in the state of Minas Gerais, Brazil.¹⁴⁵ The case study, points out as a viable option the possibility of paying (compensating) for land removed from the production process, hence giving up areas with low production potential and allocating their use to natural vegetation through ecological restoration.

Finally, the Mix category, which investigates soil pressures across the board, accounts for 32.8%. Shiferaw and Holden (2001) show that, in the Ethiopian highlands, incentives to invest in

conservation practices are very low, with the exception of low-cost methods such as grass strips.¹⁴⁶ A significant improvement in incremental gains from switching to the proposed methods occurs when the area occupied by the facilities is actually used and investment costs are subsidized. Hellin and Schrader (2003) focus on analyzing soil loss rather than soil quality to evaluate the effectiveness of soil conservation technologies and their contribution to increased production.¹⁴⁷ The research results show that the use of direct incentives to convince farmers to participate in soil and water conservation programs (SWC) is a powerful and attractive tool, but it is a very uncertain instrument for achieving the medium and long-term goals of sustainable use of territory and efficient management of natural resources. The authors conclude that direct incentives create dependency in rural communities.¹⁴⁸ Bodnar et al. (2006) evaluate the effectiveness of the donor-funded soil and water conservation (SWC) project that started in 1986 as part of the agricultural extension service in Mali.¹⁴⁹ The project aimed at large-scale adoption of SWC measures, which would eventually enable farmers to become independent of temporary donor support. The results show that erosion control measures, which depend on the specific situation of the field and the erosion problem, continued even after the subsidies were removed and spread to villages not targeted by the program. In a region in north-eastern Germany, Shuler and Sattler (2010) analyse targeted and non-targeted incentive program for reduced tillage and a restriction option in which highly erosive crops are not allowed on highly erodible field types.¹⁵⁰ The results highlight that policy changes can have an impact on soil erosion and that soil conservation policies have different levels of efficiency in terms of reducing soil erosion in relation to policy costs. In EU, Kuhlman et al. (2010) show that the on-site benefits of measures to reduce erosion on agricultural land are lower than their costs.¹⁰⁴ Similarly, the measure aimed at increasing the soil organic matter (SOM) also highlights fewer benefits on site compared to the total costs. Differently, the specific anti-compaction measure shows a positive balance due to the fact that the costs are small and the benefits on site are large. These results indicate that it is attractive for a farmer to apply these practices, because the private benefits outweigh the private costs. Moreover, the cost per hectare of the salinization measure (installation of drip irrigation) is high, but the associated risk area is small. The on-site benefits of soil protection measures in forests are less than the costs. However, the off-site benefits are large, creating a positive balance for this measure. This positive balance is the basis of public incentives to stimulate this measure by foresters. Posthumus et al. (2011) show that the Catchment Sensitive Farming (CSF), which includes both advice and capital grants, is popular with both farmers and other stakeholders, and the latter increases the effectiveness of other measures as well as providing results in itself.¹⁵¹ Anecdotal evidence on impacts is positive - for farmers, stakeholders and local supply actors - although empirical evidence is limited. In the Erlongshan River Basin, China, Sun et al (2013) provide an economically valued and market-oriented compensation standard for studying eco-compensation of environmental services and for implementing soil and water conservation at mesoscale basin scales.¹⁵² Kwayu et al. (2013) highlight how, in Tanzania, farmers engaged in the Equitable Payments for Watershed Service (EPWS) program, receive agricultural inputs, such as technical assistance and monetary rewards for

sustainable land management practices such as agroforestry and bench terracing to reduce nutrient extraction and soil erosion.¹⁵³ The researchers conclude by emphasising that in order to foster participation of smallholder farmers, attention must be paid to availability and access to information, farmer participation in program design, local compatibility of practices and support for initial adoption costs. Within the sphere of behavioral economics, in a French region, Grolleau and Mzoughi (2015), explain that public support increase for a tax on soil conservation does not depend on suggesting a future implementation, compared to an "as soon as possible" implementation.¹⁰⁶ In a wooded area of Sicily, Sgroi et al. (2016) investigate that the PES leads to an increase in the seasonal use of the forest, not only by local users but also by national and foreign visitors, promoting and enhancing the entire territory.¹⁵⁴ In Ecuador, Raes et al. (2017) point out that offering flexible contracts with different additional requirements within the same program, involving farmers from the beginning in payments for environmental service design, and combining payments for environmental services with integrated conservation and development projects may be incentives to convince more farmers to adopt silvo-pastoral systems.¹⁵⁵ Ogrodnik (2019) analyses investment expenditure on environmental protection, including soil protection.¹¹⁰ As the data analysed concern the hard coal and lignite mining sector, it is difficult to determine unambiguously whether the decrease in environmental protection expenditure is the result of the restructuring of the hard coal industry or the situation in the lignite mining sector. In the Mount Elgon region of Uganda, Geussens et al. (2019) indicate that the majority of farmers are willing to participate in a PES contract and to adopt various conservation measures, even in the absence of compensation; a minority of farmers are strongly opposed to buffer strips along the river and demand significant compensation instead.¹⁵⁶ However, farmers have strong preferences for individual over community compensation and that additional in-kind rewards in the form of labour assistance or tools increase the willingness to accept a contract. In two provinces of Burundi, Ndagijimana et al. (2020) show that the presence of soil erosion on the farm, access to credit, level of education, head of household's involvement in agriculture and age of the head of household are significantly and positively associated with higher investment in sustainable land management (SLM).¹⁵⁷ Furthermore, the findings reveal that the annual costs per farmer associated with the implementation of SLM practices require management by policymakers to facilitate access to credit markets in rural areas and to intensify efforts to strengthen the skills of smallholders, bringing more integrated and effective solutions to address the problems of land degradation. In the South Moravia region of the Czech Republic, Macháč et al. (2021) present a newly developed approach that allows monetary valuation of externalities in agriculture.¹⁵⁸ The results show that implementing adaptation measures together with subsidies are always preferable regardless of climate change scenarios and avoid societal losses. In Malawi, Ward et al. (2021) demonstrate that by providing calibrated financial incentives it is possible to substantially increase the scope and intensity of conservation agriculture (CA) adoption. Furthermore, the study highlights that a new incentive mechanism that leverages social networks to consolidate fragmented land may be more effective

in bringing more land under conservation targets, even if some of the additional land is not officially within the purview of the program PES.

2.2.2.2 Quantity-based instruments

Quantity-based instruments define a socially-optimal level of environmental goods and services or disamenities, and establish a market to redistribute them to the most efficient use in each location.¹¹¹ Only one paper falls into this category. Bicca Rodrigues et al. (2013) propose a quantification of hydrological benefits based on conservation measures within the Brazilian PES program.¹⁵⁹ The researchers investigate the option of a PES mechanism that takes into account the water storage as an improvement because it is based on water prices and can contribute to appreciation of the efforts performed by the rural producers.

2.2.2.3 Investment/disinvestments instruments

From an investment perspective, instruments to finance and promote soil health can be based on debt, equity or a combination thereof. Debt instruments, such as loans or bonds, are assets that earn interest to the creditor.¹⁶⁰ Loans are made by a bank or other financial intermediary and are repaid by the borrower over time, usually with interest. While equity financing is a monetary contribution from investors (shareholders) who wish to support the company and possibly sell their stake (ideally at a premium).¹⁶¹ The financial solutions based on the debt-equity approach are all of public origin and with a mainly regional scope of action. The result towards which they are promoted is to generate revenues.

Mustafa et al. (2021) identify the Environmental Friendly Farming (EFF) strategies and their impact on wheat crop yield, considering farmers' socioeconomic characteristics in rural Punjab. The authors shows that increasing access to agricultural credit EFF techniques may enhance farmers' financial capacity, which may help improve the adaptation of EFF strategies. Kassahun and Jacobsen (2014) use choice experiment (CE) to identify incentives that motivate land users to participate in the management of both private and communal lands so as to reduce both the on-farm and off-farm impacts of soil erosion in the Blue Nile River system.¹⁶² The results shows that access to credit is willing to contribute to the participation to soil conservation technologies (SCT). Morera and Gladwin (2006) indagate the soil conservation strategies for the hillsides of Honduras, in a neoliberal policy context with a decrease of economic incentives in agriculture.¹⁶³ The results indicate that micro-credit can substitute for off-farm work and encourage soil conservation practice. Results also indicate that credit and/or project incentives are significantly tied to the practice of conservation because although soil conservation technologies enhance productivity, they are a form of intensification requiring additional labor and often additional seed and fertilizer. Farmers do not adopt or invest in more conservation because they cannot afford to. Credit and/or incentives reduce the economic constraints that normally inhibit the application of intensification measures such as soil conservation practices. Similar findings were also found by Nyomby et al. (2006), who analyzed the strategies applied to improve soil fertility in sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁶⁴ The

results from the questionnaire, interviews and soil chemical analysis, show that credit and/or project incentives are significantly tied to the practice of conservation because although soil conservation technologies enhance productivity, they are a form of intensification requiring additional labor and often additional seed and fertilizer. Nelson and Cramb (1998) investigate the economic incentives for farmers in the Philippine uplands to adopt hedgerow intercropping relative to traditional open-field maize farming.¹⁶⁵ Cost-benefit analysis is used to compare the economic viability of different practices. The authors indicate that the efficiency of rural credit markets can potentially improve the long-term economic viability of sustainable agricultural practices by reducing farmers' cost of capital and discount rates. Furthermore, two other elements are considered important: the expansion of the existing network of government-sponsored agricultural cooperatives, which can reduce the cost of capital for farmers if transaction costs are reduced; and the elimination of trade protection, which could be one of the most effective soil conservation strategies available to the government, reducing incentives to produce corn over less erosive crops. Lingkubi and Leitch (1996) assess the economics of soil conservation in Todano watershed in Indonesia.¹⁶⁶ Using a benefit cost framework the results highlight the low participation of farmers in using soil conservation practices, this is partly due to the inability to integrate soil conservation practices, since their income is not adequate to cover the start-up costs of the soil conservation measures. Furthermore, farmers may be unwilling to adopt soil conservation practices due to lack of knowledge, technical skills or lack of expectation of long-term economic returns.

2.2.2.4 Insurance-related instruments

The insurance within the field of agriculture works as the market insurance: the land manager redistributes income, by managing natural capital, towards securing income flows in hazardous states.¹⁶⁷ Solutions based on insurance models were investigated for the total (100%) by hypothetical studies applying ex ante evaluations. Beneficiaries' preferences towards a set of financial solutions including other types are assessed.

Palm-Forster et al. (2016) analyze farmer preferences for different types of financial incentives for voluntary conservation, including direct payments, insurance, tax credits, and stewardship certification benefits.¹⁶⁸ Results from the experimental auctions suggested that, because of low perceived transaction costs, direct payments and tax credits were more cost-effective conservation incentives than best management practice insurance. Langpap (2004) explores the theme of optimal design strategy for implementing incentives programs in order to increase participation in conservation programs.¹⁶⁹ The results show that targeting incentives such as cost sharing agreements, public recognition and stewardship certification may be effective in increasing participation rates among younger landowners who have acquired property more recently. The study of Marenya et al. (2014) use a framed choice experiment to examine Malawian smallholder farmers' preferences among four major policy options that provide incentives for adopting agroforestry-based conservation practices: cash payments, an ideal crop insurance instrument that corresponds relatively closely to insurance contracts tied to a farm's actual yields, a crop insurance

instrument with a 50% basis risk, and fertilizer subsidies.¹⁷⁰ Almost no farmer opted to use traditional farming practices when confronted with cash payment, insurance contract, and/or fertilizer subsidy-based incentives for the adoption of conservation agriculture. This suggests that the scope for such incentive programs is substantial once the full effects of these practices are taken into account. Furthermore the study provides some support for the hypothesis that cash and liquidity constraints may limit farmers' willingness to use crop insurance as a risk management tool.¹⁷⁰ The link between insurance and environmental impact in agrarian systems requires understanding of how insurance mitigates the influence of uncertainty on a farmer's well-being.¹⁷¹ Indeed, some studies^{172,173} show that farmers tend to engage in riskier and more intensive farming practices (e.g. use more fertilisers, pesticides, etc.) when they purchase agricultural insurance.¹⁷¹

2.2.2.5 Regulatory instruments

Regulatory instruments are any instrument or approach that involves regulatory reform such as a change in laws, policies, regulations and/or enforcement.¹⁰⁰ As reported by Pirard (2012), market-based instruments, such as taxes, charges or tradable permits, can, if carefully designed and implemented, complement regulations by changing economic incentives, and therefore the behavior of private actors, when deciding on use of resources. If set at accurate levels, they ensure that beneficiaries of biodiversity and ecosystem services pay the full cost of providing the services.¹⁷⁴ The papers analysed show that the regulatory instruments are totally addressed to land users, with the aim of regulating their land use practices. The majority of the analysed regulatory instruments operate at the national scale 44.4%, followed by the local scale 33.3%, the regional scale 16.7% and finally the global scale 5.6%. This distribution makes sense as the majority of rules and regulations are in the hands of national government bodies and institutions, which local and regional governments are inspired by. The majority of regulatory instruments act in the sphere of pressures on soil properties dimension, particularly in the sustainable use of land practices (61.2%). Jia et al. (2022) analysed the effects of the China's Sloping land conversion program (SLCP) on the land tenure practices of farmers who benefited from incentives in the form of PES and converted sloping agricultural land into forest land.¹⁷⁵ The main objective was to renew farmland, stop farming on sloping farmland prone to soil erosion in a planned and orderly manner, and restore forest vegetation according to local conditions. The results show how the SLCP policy helped to alleviate the pressure of socio-economic factors on soil conservation improvement. Li et al. (2022) studied the optimisation of the economic protection compensation standard by adding the value of the ecosystem services of cultivated land in order to comprehensively assess the resources of cultivated land and correct for externalities.¹⁷⁶ By combining the values of ecosystem services and the quality index, they determined the new county-level compensation standard for cropland protection in the Hangzhou Bay area (China). The results show that there are clear regional disparities in the value of ecosystem services of cultivated land, which means that there are significant differences in the capacity for sustainable use of cultivated land. This latter aspect highlights the need to establish graduated compensation standards in the region that take into

account different land-use practices. Kahsay et al. (2022) study the effects of the Food-for-Work (FFW) program in Ethiopia.¹⁷⁷ The researchers show how the program affects both development and environmental aspects by mitigating individuals' consumption during shocks (e.g. drought) and helping to build assets, which in turn can reduce pressure on natural resources and promote environmental rehabilitation using community labour. However, such a program can have unintended consequences in excluding pro-environmental behavior and weakening collective action. Therefore, understanding the exact channel through which food incentives can crowd out pro-environmental behaviors is very important in designing public programs that aim to mitigate these effects. Saad et al. (2021) investigates the implementation of a PES incentive programme in the Serra da Mantiquera area (Brazil), which regulates land-use practices through the increase of forested area and the construction of small retention basins.¹²⁴ The programme's development scenario is tested by modelling the difference in transported sediment. Results showed that increased forest cover combined with soil conservation practices led to a decrease in soil loss and sediment export. Alix-Garcia et al. (2021) studied the impacts of conservation payments in the context of communal applicants to Mexico's federal payments for ecosystem services program, which started in 2003.¹⁷⁸ The program's primary goal is to conserve forest or other vegetative cover in areas threatened by conversion or degradation. It offers annual payments per hectare over 5-year periods to private and communal landowners. In exchange for the funds, landowners must maintain existing forest or natural land cover and engage in land management activities such as building fences, controlling pests, or patrolling for illegal activity. The key national program using financial incentives to promote the conservation of municipal lands has led to policy relevant increases in land cover management activities. Researchers found increased levels of community social capital as a result of Mexico's PES program and no changes in family trust or participation. Such findings from the perspective of public regulation demonstrate that it is possible to compensate communities for their management efforts without harming social cooperation or weakening existing institutions. Arias et al. (2011) analyse the Cambodian government's options in the future scenario for the implementation of public regulations in the context of hydropower production.¹⁷⁹ In particular they applied a modelling framework to estimate the economic value of forest conservation and sustainable forest management. The calculated values are then used to establish a baseline for PES scheme and policy framework that pay for forest conservation in the upstream part of the watershed that supplies water to the hydropower facility. The results of the simulation shows that the forest conservation practices reduce sedimentation and provide services for hydropower beneficiaries. The cost benefit derived from the evaluation of the most conservative forest option was used to construct the PES financial mechanism and its policy and regulatory components. The study by Kurkalova et al. (2004) compares the relative efficiency of alternative targeting schemes for least-cost incentive payment policies that offer subsidies to farmers in exchange for adopting conservation tillage.¹⁸⁰ For the State of Iowa, an estimate is made of the costs and benefits of policies aimed at conserving acreage, carbon sequestration in agricultural soils, reducing nitrogen runoff, reducing soil erosion by of water and the reduction of

soil erosion by wind. The results show that the budgets for the policies to be implemented are large, there may be no need to implement performance-based subsidy policies, whose monitoring costs could be high. The study by Shiferaw and Holden (2000) analyzes some policy instruments to mitigate the soil erosion externality using empirical data from Ethiopia.¹⁴⁶ The results show that policies that link production subsidies with soil conservation can provide opportunities for countering erosion-induced productivity declines without adverse impacts on marketed surplus of food and the welfare of the poor. Such policies may, therefore, represent improvements in efficiency, equity, and environmental quality. When unlinked input subsidies are provided, the enhanced profitability of farming discourages the need to conserve the soil stock and thus conservation disappears as the subsidy increases. As previously found by Kahsay et al. (2022) using domestic labor through incentive contracts, such as food-for-work programs, can be an effective approach for soil conservation. Starting from the consideration that the economic literature does not provide a clear answer to the question of whether structural adjustment programs contribute to soil conservation, Bulte and Van Soest (1999) analyze the impact of an aspect of many structural adjustment programs (mitigating "rural prejudice" by increasing relative prices for agricultural outputs) on soil depth in the context of a model that allows investment in soil regeneration.¹⁸¹ Researchers show that higher prices help maintain thicker soils when agricultural producers face a series of perfect markets for their inputs and outputs. At the same time they underline that if the restrictive hypothesis of perfect markets is relaxed, the increase in prices can have both positive and negative effects on the depth of the soil, depending on the elasticity of the marginal utility of the purchased consumer goods. When the absolute value of this elasticity exceeds unity, producers should respond to the price increase by reducing their labor input invested in soil regeneration to restore equilibrium. Therefore, there may be a potential conflict between price reform and soil conservation. Pagiola (1996) examine empirically how policy-induced price changes affect the incentive of farmers to adopt soil conservation measures.⁸⁸ The results shows that there is no simple relationship between price distortions created by the government policies and farmers' incentives to adopt conservation measures. the researchers underline how the results obtained from the research partly support the key role of regulatory rules especially in cases where market failures occur, given that on the contrary, if the prices received by farmers accurately reflected social opportunity costs of resources, private conservation decisions would be efficient: socially beneficial conservation practices would be adopted and socially unprofitable conservation practices would be rejected. In practice, markets are not perfect and prices are often distorted. Some regulatory mechanisms have focused on pressures affecting the soil service dimension, such as biodiversity loss and watershed conditions. Guo et al. (2022) identified the spatial biodiversity heterogeneity of grassland degradation risk using Future Land Use Simulation (FLUS) model, then incorporated grassland degradation risk as a criterion into PES spatial targeting using cost–benefit analysis and ranking optimization.¹⁸² The results empirically showed the relevance in identifying the spatial model of the risk of degradation of grasslands in relation to the spatial model of the additional environmental benefits obtained through PES in order to select the areas where to direct

the PES with the aim of conserving the biodiversity of the ecosystem considered. Viani et al. (2019) analysed the application of the Forest and landscape restoration (FLR) strategy for large-scale tropical forest recovery, and payment for ecosystem services (PES) used to support FLR programs and projects on privately-owned land within the Water Producer Project in the Atlantic Forest in Brazil.¹⁸³ The results shows that schemes are more complex than initially thought, and that sufficient funding does not guarantee the success of FLR projects. Eiswerth and Van Kooten (2019) investigate the issue of externalities between managers as a potentially important topic in the design and implementation of payments for water ecosystem services (PWES) and examine the implications of accounting for externalities using different analytical frameworks.¹⁸⁴ The results show that when a land manager implements a PWES-funded best management practice (BMP) designed to produce an ES, this BMP affects the 'marginal ecosystem service product' (MESP) of other land managers, both in the same catchment and in other catchments, but who are not currently engaged in the PWES market.

Finally, the rest of the regulatory mechanisms have focused on pressures affecting the soil function dimension, such as erosion and eutrophication. Aradóttir et al. (2013) analysing financial solutions and mechanisms in Iceland from 1907 to 2010.¹⁰⁹ The majority of ecological restoration projects and programs in Iceland have been funded by the government. Laws and policies were primarily identified as drivers when they resulted in special funding efforts, such as the "gift of the nation" or designated programs to stimulate carbon sequestration. Prager et al. (2011) analyzed the impact of soil conservation policies on farming practices and on the mitigation of soil degradation in Uckermark region (Germany).¹⁸⁵ The findings highlighted the potential of incentive-based policies – such as agri-environment programs – to promote the adoption of targeted conservation measures that reduce land degradation. At the same time, the authors highlight how land degradation addressed only by regulatory policy instruments and EU-based national regulations greatly limits the effectiveness of the measures. Pedroso et al. (2007) address the effects of erosion on the environmental services provided by the soil and explore possibilities for integrating soil erosion impacts in cost–benefit analyses of agri-environmental policies in Southern Portugal. The results show that practices that reduce tillage as established by the Zonal Program of Castro Verde (ZPCV) show margins for reducing soil erosion. Goetz and Keusch (2005) analyzed the optimal intertemporal management of soil and phosphorus losses from agricultural land.¹⁸⁶ Through the analysis and comparison of three different abatement policies, the researchers show that one indirect policy in the form of land protection scores (SPS) is highly inefficient, while another indirect policy in the form of land use taxes soil is almost as efficient as an abatement policy direct politics. Botterweg et al. (1998) analyzed the effect of different policy measures on erosion and nutrient losses.¹⁸⁷ The results shows that the effect of policy measure intended to reduce nonpoint source pollution strongly differ both between years and areas. Furthermore, differences in the effects of various policies across geographic regions may imply that a differentiated policy is warranted.

2.2.3 Conclusions

The analysis of the literature has highlighted how the use of economic instruments in the field of soil health is generally still a dispersed field of research. Economic and fiscal instruments indirectly address soil health, despite the issue of land use sustainability being at the centre of the narrative and political agenda. As regards the methods used, in the present analysis it emerged that half of the methods used in the papers make use of qualitative and mixed models and approaches, while the other half use quantitative methods. Empirical research is therefore a field of analysis that can be explored further in the future. Regarding the specific analysis of economic instruments, the literature review identified instruments that receive less attention in land use management, such as insurance related instruments and quantity-based instruments. While price-based instruments are abundantly analyzed and explored in depth on the ground, within which PES, subsidies and economic incentives represent the majority of economic solutions. The strong focus on price-based instruments can be seen as a specific characteristic of research on economic instruments in the context of land use management, as was also found by Ackerschott et al. (2023).¹⁰² Also Ackerschott points out that this aspect is relevant in consideration of the fact that the role of subsidies and compensation payments are tools widely discussed with respect to their effectiveness and their effects on productivity and management strategies towards land users.^{102,188} Another result of the review was to find particular attention to agricultural land conservation practices followed by the sustainable management of forests and watersheds, while the issues of land use transformation in urban environments have been little investigated.

With reference to the character of the economic instruments, we found a deficiency in the analysis of the economic evaluation of the instruments taken into consideration within the papers. In 60.5% of cases no economic evaluations are made. In this regard, it would be useful to understand how the potential development of a particular economic instrument can impact from the point of view of economic development and its political feasibility.

3 Ex-post performance assessment of selected instruments

The previous sections 1 and 2 refers to the first part of Task 6.1 which consisted of a mapping review of European, national and regional policy requirements and incentives aiming at or encouraging management of and investments in soil health. Section 3 focuses on the second part of Task 6.1 which included undertaking semi-structured interviews with 15-20 knowledgeable experts and representatives of organizations involved in implementation of policy and economic schemes. This section aims to capture views and interpretations on existing policy and financial mechanisms supporting protection, rehabilitation and restoration of healthy soil. This section is structured as following: subsection 3.1 explores the method applied during the interviewing process; subsection

3.2 discusses the main results retrieved by the empirical study; and subsection 3.3 draws some conclusions.

3.1 Method

In November and December 2023, 15 virtual semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather information and perspectives relating to the WP6 objectives set out above in Section 1. Interviews helped to develop a comprehensive understanding of incentives and nudges contributing to preserving and restoring soil health in policy and practice.

The interview process firstly consisted of contacting LL and LH partners in charge. They were asked to provide a list of potential participants, including policy makers, scientific community, land managers, businesses, farmers/ farm organizations and industries. Secondly, the potential participants were contacted by email and provided with the Interview Protocol.

The Interview Protocol firstly provides some information about the project. It provides potential participants with guiding interview questions. It explains the type of the involvement in interviews, risks and benefits of being involved in the study, and rights as a participant. Finally, it encloses the consent form to be filled out and signed before the interview.

Participation in interviews involved typically 40-60 minutes, with a series of questions on the following themes: policy incentives and nudges contributing to preserving and restoring soil health.

The guiding interview questions were:

1. a) With which types of soil pressures and soil degradation are you dealing with on a regular basis in your role/organisation, if any? b) What is your understanding of and experience with soil pressures and soil degradation? Can you give some examples?
2. a) Are you familiar with policies or financial mechanisms taking into account soil health? What specific benefits and opportunities do they bring, if any? b) Can you share examples of (local/regional/national/EU-wide) policy and economic mechanisms that consider protection, rehabilitation and restoration?
3. Are there any barriers or challenges you think decision-makers are facing in implementing soil health policies and economic instruments in sectors/areas you are familiar with? Can you give some examples?
4. What potential trade-offs or synergies do you anticipate or have experienced in the development or implementation of policies and economic instruments that take into account protection, rehabilitation and restoration of soil?

Interviews were conducted remotely using Zoom platform and recorded. Recording was not shared in the project. The involvement in an interview were not disclosed in research outputs, unless participants wish to be acknowledged.

Interviews may include discussion of the effectiveness of policies and financial solutions relating to preserving and restoring soil health. Some participants, depending on the national and sectoral

context, may find it uncomfortable to reflect on this theme. Participants can choose not to answer particular questions (without stating a reason), and all responses given will be anonymised.

While there are no personal benefits from involvement in this study, participation could help the research team to strengthen their understanding of academic, policy, and industry perspectives on preserving and restoring soil health.

Regarding the rights as a participant, taking part in the study is voluntary. Declining to participate will have no negative consequences for participants and their organisations.

The final 15 participants include: 2 from Italy, 4 from Switzerland, 4 from Spain, 2 from Croatia, 1 from Lithuania, 1 from Latvia, 1 from Netherland. Three interviewees were policy makers, six from the scientific community, one farmer/land manager, one land manager and four from businesses (Table 3).

Interviewee	Category	Country	LL/LH
Int.1	Scientific community	Croatia	LH4
Int.2	Land manager	Spain	LH1, LH2, LH3
Int.3	Scientific community	Spain	LH1, LH2, LH3
Int.4	Businesses	Italy	LL1
Int.5	Businesses	Italy	LL1
Int.6	Policymaker	Lithuania	LH5
Int.7	Farmer/Land manager	Croatia	LH4
Int.8	Scientific community	Spain	LH1, LH2, LH3
Int.9	Scientific community	Netherlands	LL3
Int.10	Businesses	Switzerland	LL2
Int.11	Scientific community	Switzerland	LL2
Int.12	Scientific community	Spain	LH1, LH2, LH3
Int.13	Policymaker	Switzerland	LL2
Int.14	Policymaker	Latvia	LH6
Int.15	Businesses	Switzerland	LL2

Table 3 Category and country of participants.

3.2 Discussion

The analysis of empirical data revealed the thoughts and perspectives on existing policy incentives and nudges contributing to preserving and restoring soil health. This analysis contributed to develop a comprehensive understanding of policy and financial mechanisms supporting healthy soil in both policy and practice. Subsection 3.2.1 introduces the facts, i.e. types of soil pressures and soil degradation understood and experienced by participants. Subsection 3.2.2 explores policies and financial mechanisms addressing those pressures at multiple level, particularly examining benefits and opportunities. Subsection 3.2.3 reflects on the implementation of those mechanisms

by investigating barriers and challenges. Subsection 3.2.4 considers potential trade-offs and synergies in the development or implementation of policies and economic instruments that consider protection, rehabilitation and restoration of soil.

3.2.1 Understanding of and experience with types of soil pressures and soil degradation

This subsection explores the main types of soil pressures and soil degradation that participants from LLs and LHs related countries have identified as significant in their areas of experience and sectors (Table 4). This subsection examines only the main pressures considered by participants, including erosion and contamination/pollution.

In Sardinia region (Italy), November is statistically the rainiest month, hence the soils are very often exposed to erosion phenomena and in the worst cases landslide flood events [Int. 4 businesses, Int. 5 businesses]. In Switzerland, there is huge flooding and a high soil erosion gradient is registered because of lot of hilly or mountainous arable areas. The main problem is soil erosion when there are large water bodies [Int. 10 businesses, Int. 11 scientific community; Int. 13 policy maker; Int.15 businesses]. In Spain, because of physic and biotic conditions of soil, erosion and the loss of soil, especially in the fertility of soil is a problem [Int. 2 land manager; int. 8 scientific community]. However, there is not appropriate Regional or even State policy about this problem. Only the CAP is addressing it, but obviously it is not only according to national context, rather in terms of the wider Europe context. The problem of erosion in this context of olive orchards is especially dramatic [Int. 2 land manager]. In Croatia and Latvia, erosion is mainly caused by wind [Int. 1 scientific community, Int. 4 policy maker], whereas in Lithuania by unsustainable use of soil [Int. 6 policy maker].

In Switzerland, contamination is perpetrated trough different polluters. Agricultural land pressures include mainly fertilizer application of plant protection products, but also chemicals from the air. However, all the heavy metals are less of a concern nowadays except cooper in nine yards. [Int. 13 policy makers]. In Spain, there is an excess of animal manure linked to micro farms and the poultry industry, which are reaching saturation in soils with the issue of slurry, nitrate contamination, etc. In livestock farming, the chronic use of antiparasitic and other synthetic medications in livestock is also affecting the health of soil. [Int.3 scientific community]. Use of glyphosate and another herbicide decreases soil fertility, because carbon is not fixed in the soil and soil erosion [Int. 8 scientific community]. In Southwest Spain, the use of herbicides has been relevant in recent years [Int.2 land manager]. In Sardinia (Italy), the risk of pollution is directly linked to agriculture. The problem with nitrate pollution is that this has repercussions on the aquifer and therefore on waterways [Int.4 businesses]. In Croatia, pollution is not related to the agricultural soil, but with managing of the waste or some trash, more related to not properly managed [Int.1 scientific community]. The most percentage of pollution is coming from manure, because framers are having a diary farms, and then they have too many cows per hectare [Int.7 farmer/land manager].

Soil pressure	Italy (LL1)	Switzerland (LL2)	Netherlands (LL3)	Spain (LH1, LH2, LH3)	Croatia (LH4)	Lithuania (LH5)	Latvia (LH6)
Overgrazing	x						
Erosion	x	x		x	x	X	x
Plowing	x						
Unused land, abandonment of large lands	x			x			
Contamination/pollution	x	x	x	x	x	X	
Risk of desertification	x						
Installation of photovoltaic system	x		x	x	x		
Marginal areas where many companies continued to carry out superficial work on steeply sloping terrain.	x						
Compaction		x			x		
Sealing		X					
Lack of organic matter		X		x	x		
Biodiversity decline		x					
Stressed structure, bare soil and damaged surface		x		x			
Use of heavy machinery		x		x	x		X
Depleted of nutrients			x				
Soil water issues			x				
Drought				x			
Gas extraction			x				
Loss of fertility				x			
Mining				x			x
Very intensive farming methods						X	

Cultivation of monoculture						X	
Monitoring issue							x
Lack of state mechanisms					x		

Table 4 Types of soil pressures and soil degradation that identified as significant in LLs and LHs related countries.

Participants from Italy, Netherlands, Spain and Croatia, consider the installation of photovoltaic system a pressure for the soil [Int.4 businesses; Int.3 scientific community; Int.1 scientific community; Int.9 Scientific community; Int. 8 scientific community]. In Spain, renewable energies specifically with large photovoltaic parks and photovoltaics comes into conflict with food security strategies [Int.3 scientific community]. Now with photovoltaic is happening also in Croatia because people want to earn money [Int.1 scientific community]. Solar panel deplete the soil underneath which suddenly is destroyed, or the ecosystem shifts into a new ecosystem [Int.9 scientific community] Use of heavy machinery has also been stressed as a type of soil pressure. In Switzerland, the machinery is increasing with the weight (heavy tractors) [Int.13 policy maker]. In Croatia, farmers are using traditional mechanization. They create compacted soil because they deteriorate the structure, and they are using heavy machinery and plugging to loosen that soil [Int.1 scientific community]. In Latvia, heavy machinery is more popular currently [Int.4 policy maker] In Spain, machinery and tools have not been economically improved and not tested on women. Less impacting measures machines and machinery or innovation are not taken into account [Int.8 scientific community]

Lack of organic matter has been also pointed out as soil pressure by interviewees from Switzerland, Spain and Croatia [Int.10 businesses, Int.15 businesses; Int.8 scientific community; Int.1 scientific community; Int.7 [farmer/land manager]. North Spain has a lower pH, the Mediterranean soils are alkaline and with higher risk of losing organic matter, hence there is a higher rate of mineralization [Int.8 scientific community]. In Croatia, a very low organic matter is viewed the most important process of soil degradation. Farmers think about the soil as a substrate which can be used just for growing plants and not as something that is worth to keep in quality manner and to increase the quality. There is not enough organic matter to keep the structure well [Int.1 scientific community]. The pH of soil is very low because of growing only one culture, mostly corn because of our livestock [Int.7 farmer/land manager].

This subsection showed that countries are experiencing more than twenty different soil pressures. In addition, the soil structure differs from a country to another one, hence the impacts of these pressure may be different. The next subsection examines to what extent policy and economic instruments address those pressures at multiple level and scale in order to protect, rehabilitate and restore soil health.

3.2.2 Benefits and opportunities of policies or financial mechanisms that consider protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of soil health

After having discussed the main types of soil pressures, participants shared their thoughts on benefits and opportunities of policies and/or financial mechanisms that contribute to the protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of soil health. As Table 5 shows, the EU CAP is the main instrument mentioned by participants.

Country	Policy and economic instrument	Benefits/Opportunities
Italy (LL1)	Programma di Sviluppo Rurale	Income support measures.
	CAP	Maximize profit while respecting the environment.
Switzerland (LL2)	CAP	Subsidies for green/crop cover. Direct payments for agriculture.
	Carbon credits from private sectors	Compensation.
	Carbon sequestration and biodiversity targets	Measures such as reducing cultivation on peat soils and drainage rating of peat soils and using animal manure on fields.
	Ordinance of soil protection	Three value system for many of chemical pollution.
	Soil protection on construction sites	Collaboration of administration science and practice.
	Ecological compliance orders	Friendly ecological practices.
Netherlands (LL3)	Farming regulations	Public management organizations.
Spain (LH1, LH2, LH3)	CAP and Eco scheme	Orchards cover soil management. Mandatory carbon stock measurement. Agriculture conservation.
	Carbon credits from private sectors	Environmental and soil conservation if the mechanism is applied properly.
	Nature restoration law (EU)	Measurement of soil health.
	EU habitat directive	Livestock management as fundamental for the conservation of some ecosystems
Croatia (LH4)	CAP and Eco scheme	Biodiversity protection.
	National policy	Big farmers and entrepreneurs advantaged.
Lithuania (LH5)	Order of the minister related to the sustainable use of soil	Collaboration among all relevant ministers.
	National plan	Consultations between farmers and scientists.

Latvia (LH6)	CAP strategic plan (social strategy)	Sustainability tool. Soil analysis. Restoration activities.
	Nature restoration law (EU)	Organic soil restoration, target, monitoring.
	Carbon removal schemes from private sector	GHG reporting needs.

Table 5 Benefits and opportunities of policies or financial mechanisms that consider protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of soil health.

In Italy, Int.4 [businesses] explains that the conditionality in the CAP is a series of good agricultural practices of mandatory management criteria that ensure that there are essential conditions for the company to receive funding.⁵² These practices include avoiding working on certain slopes and near rivers. Int.5 [businesses] affirms that both national and regional policies have addressed mandatory and optional measures to protect and improve fertility. The so-called mandatory conditionality includes even slightly more restrictive rotations to link both the economic aspect and the function of the soil. The optional conditionality gives additional reward, which is also additional commitment, i.e. respecting certain rotations. The objective that should be achieved is that companies can maximize profit which is a corporate objective while respecting the environment.

Int.11 [scientific community] explains that the cover crops are included into the national subsidies scheme for farmers in Switzerland and in the EU CAP. In Switzerland and in the EU there are schemes that supports organic agriculture for example, but they are not specifically addressing soil health as a policy.

Int.2 [land manager] also refers to the EU CAP and eco scheme which established the objectives and then the member states must adapt. In Spain, there is one eco scheme that is how to manage the cover soil of the orchards. However, husbandry is not considered as an option to keep under control the cover in orchards. Indeed, the Spanish eco scheme does not consider managing properly the animals through a grazing plan to keep under control the cover and obtain the products of the husbandry itself. The problem is the density and also especially the time the animals are kept in the area and also the recovery time which is not considered in this eco scheme. The previous version of the operative program which regulates all the CAP in Spain included a secondary eco scheme which was "Agricultura de precisión y ganadería de precisión", i.e. smart husbandry and smart agriculture associated with high tech techniques and practices.

Int.3 [scientific community] explains that the Spanish Ministry is echoing the need to analyze the capacity of soils to sequester carbon, since the European Union and the European Commission have already presented new legislation on how the collection of carbon credits will be regulated. For example, the analysis of the capacity of soils to sequester carbon can be done in very different ways depending on the resources that are applied and the criteria or calculation tools that are used to date. For example, look at another topic that has to do with economies private initiatives to declare the carbon footprint of some products. That is the only way in which activities that are linked to environmental and soil conservation come out well in that carbon footprint calculation.

Payment for carbon credits, types of care for regenerative soils, etc., will be beneficial or not for the soils depending on how it is applied. However, if in the long term it only depletes the soil and causes loss and generation, the application of incentive mechanisms can be counterproductive. The interests of large corporations are usually preferred and sometimes they make the rules not adapted well to the reality of small family productions, which do not have as much lobbying capacity, but are really the ones that are linked to conservation.

Int. 12 [scientific community] explains that the CAP is also mandatory to measure the carbon stock. In the Spanish CAP, there are also eco schemes for agriculture conservation. However, the use of that kind of farming systems always means the use of herbicides. Therefore, the structure is kept, but the soil is killed. There is a big lobby pushing for that system to be included in this kind of policies like carbon farming or like CAP and finally our Ministry of Agriculture decided that they will make an evaluation in 2025 and they will assess what happened with that Echo scheme, by measuring the carbon stock in the different ecosystems. This sort of clarification is essential for a good implementation of policies in order to address the paradox of keeping carbon in the soil, while destroying biodiversity.

Int. 8 [scientific community] underlines that the CAP establishes Spanish legal framework apart from being a fund resource. The police could have a good positive influence on soil protection and improvement, but the problem comes when implementing. The first draft of the current CAP is a very ambitious one, but it was achievable, because it is not banning the use of products accompanying the transition for farmers with public funds. However, the current CAP has also helped the concentration of land and farming rights in fewer hands, which means that in most territories is not actually farms, but companies. Moreover, in most of member states, they have made sure that every territory received the same amount of money that they had before and almost every CAP beneficiary could apply at least one eco scheme. The second pillar on the agri-environmental measures has less funds. Moreover, the funds are allocated for organic through even cover the current actors that are being growing in organic. All agricultural measures and policies are usually based on the definition of farms and the annual own work unit, which is the European definition, i.e. how much you have got to work to keep you busy in a year and to give you a salary more or less. This is a very simplified definition. But when it comes to member states and territories to check if farmers are fulfilling the requirements for an annual work unit, they do not just take it on account. The number of vectors you are cultivating, if you are intercropping, if you are rotating, if you are doing your own input, if you are selling the products that you get from the farm or from the first transformation. This is the definition in horizontal regulation, but they do not take that on account. This is also the first bottleneck where you exclude all small farmers that are really diversifying their production and closing those nutrient cycles. Because of all this extra time that they are investing, this is not taken into account. We are actually excluding those that are doing that when you identify best practices and you see who will be out of the CAP measures.

As part of the EU, Croatia adopted CAP and several eco schemes for example diversification of agricultural land, intensive pasture management, use of organic fertilizers on arable crop plants

and one which is related to the soil health is conservative agriculture [Int.1 scientific community]. These eco schemes involve reduced tillage, broader crop rotation, mulches integrity of weed management and education of the farmers how to deal with it. If farmers adopt this eco scheme is conservative agriculture. It can bring him around 175 to 325 euros per hectare per year. The Advisory service in Croatia has to check if he is really dealing with that, if he is adopting those practices. After the check, he can receive that amount of money. For all these eco schemes, it works like it can be covered if he has some more costs. For adopting these practices, those costs can be also covered by the government. The increase of the organic farming could be also part of the soil health. Currently we have around 9% of arable land is under the ecological agriculture and we would like to increase it to 14/15 percent to the 2030. This is also something that government is supporting by investing in it and paying for the increase of ecological practices in agriculture. This is something that is about the common agricultural practices and what is related to soil conservation or soil health. The main thing is that this is about minimal requirements which are prescribed by common agricultural practices. Besides this financial opportunity that the government will pay for them, there are opportunity for the biodiversity, but the soil is currently without organic matter or very low organic matter. Therefore, farmers have to wait for several years and in that period, they will have problems with weeds and no lower yields. Forms of compensation such as carbon credits just occur within projects and not on the state level.

In Latvia, in the social strategy, there is emphasis of sustainability tool which is under the CAP. There is also quite a significant part of soil analysis embedded in our CAP strategic plan in order to receive support, you how to do soil analysis [Int.4 policy maker].

Regarding forms of compensation such as carbon credits, in Switzerland, on the national level, farmers do not receive carbon credits, but there are a lot of initiatives from the private sector to issue carbon credits. There is a private project where a bank is actually financing carbon credits. There are also private companies which are currently working on those carbon credits. The methodology for soil carbon sequestration is quite challenging and unsure if it is the best way to go with compensation instead of reduction. Carbon credit schemes are developing. For the targets, of course the national policy states have targets for carbon sequestration and for soil health and they are partly separated between climate related targets and culture related more generally ecosystem service provided. About soil carbon sequestration, they are mainly related to the policy targets of the climate from the national government. They have not quantified this, how much they want to increase soil carbon sequestration within the next years, but they have set some measures like for example reducing cultivation on peat soils and drainage rating of peat soils and using animal manure on fields [Int.11 scientific community]. In a Swiss canton, there is a quite bug program (involving 100 hectares and 452 growers) which pays their growers for the delta increase of organic soil matter. This is challenging because you have to measure the baseline data correctly. The program is financed by a local bank for CO₂ compensation, and this is a little bit questionable, because if you add the soil organic matter, you do not take the CO₂ from the planet, it is not a complete real sequestration. However, thanks to the provision of specific advice and strategy,

farmers started to work differently with their soils and with the equipment very good [Int. 10 businesses]. Int. 15 [businesses] has a mixed opinion on compensation from CO₂. From a side, that is a quite good financial help for more implementation, from another one, in 20-50 years it is impossible to get high compensation right, because you cannot take more organic matter.

In Latvia [Int. 4 policymakers] explains that the National Forest Research Institute is working with a model from Scandinavia to measure carbon content in agriculture and in forest soil, which is very important in terms of GHG reporting needs and to save money. Although that is still under discussion, there are several initiatives already when carbon removal schemes are operating on private basis and at national level the Ministry of climate and energy are working on national climate law. The Carbon Removal Certification system should provide incentives. Experts are working during next year on specific methodologies at a low level and private companies are already engaged with landowners.

Int.12 [scientific community] affirms that in Spain with education framework there is room for carbon farming activities. The Commission is preparing a regular framework to regulate the voluntary carbon market in Europe and Spain is working to push the Commission to include wetlands because they always look at peatlands. There is a lot of room there to include soil health parameters.

The EU nature restoration law has also been mentioned by participants from Spain and Latvia.¹⁸⁹ They wanted to include an indicator to measure the carbon stock in the soil. A measurement in soil is going to be mandatory to assess the state of ecosystems and the health of soil. Financing is needed to implement projects, involving the restoration for instance of wetlands. They are working to create a methodology for a standard to compensate absorption of CO₂ projects. The Commission is preparing now this packet to set up the main criteria that the standards must compliment not comply to be able to operate in Europe which are quality and sustainability. All the projects that are involved can be certified under one standard for carbon removal. However, those kinds of projects have a big impact on biodiversity hence they are not going to be possible in the future. The commission is trying to score or give more points to those kinds of projects that improve the sustainability, great areas, for biodiversity and for water, for adaptation to climate and other criteria and more over than mitigation to climate change what they call co-benefits and soil health will be one of those criteria [Int. 12 scientific community]. Regarding the EU habitat directive, at least 6,161 habitats on the list of habitats are affected by an issue called agricultural or livestock management for the maintenance of its biodiversity and its good state of conservation.¹⁹⁰ Indeed, work for the livestock site is necessary for the correct maintenance of these habitats. Therefore, within this directive, habitat (and restoration) is understood as the livestock management being fundamental for the conservation of some ecosystems [Int.12 scientific community]. Switzerland has a biodiversity target, i.e. 7% area is devoted to biodiversity soil health which is always debated because of the loss of lot of organic matter [Int.15 businesses] Restoration activities is also mentioned in strategy and for organic soil in Latvia [Int.14 policymaker]. Ph soil is important, and this goes together with Nature Restoration Law where particular targets still under discussion, but it is

at the final stage. A big issue in Latvia about organic soil restoration and how to fulfil this target. Monitoring is what is mentioned again in the social strategy. It goes together with soil data gathering and analysis, but it is important to how the data about carbon sequestration, organic carbon level and for forest as well as agricultural, so it should be monitored in Latvia. We are in better situation with agricultural soil because they had several projects already so monitoring system is in establishment phase for agricultural land. However, since forest focus regulation has expired and IPCC, the forest activities or not anymore ongoing in forest land, we have very little data about for a source. This is a point where we do look for national funding or we are discussing right now within institutions nationally and you need to attract other funding just to know better or follow-up what is going on this forest soils. It is much better with soil monitoring of big types of soils organic and mineral. But we are in a much worse situation with forest. We do not have stable funding right now together with forest soil information data. Although we are informed about updated rules of regulation where countries are requested to provide detailed information about many aspects of those and including also carbon content and we should identify carbon rich soils and do it in your reference approach. Need for data is urgent but funding need is as well as urgent to be able to go. Int.9 [scientific community] refers to Dutch regulations on farming, including the typical example of ground water usage. However, the participant believes that, if two-thirds of Netherlands exists below sea level, further rules and organizational schemes are needed to protect the health of water and therefore also the health of soil. There are public management organizations that have regulatory power hence they represent an additional layer above cities or regions. These water management organizations are responsible for all waterways in their region. They can also make local regulations and legislation that have the force of law. There is a democratic representation, hence they have elections for the governing board of this water management companies, and they are ruled by farmers. There is the tension between profit interest of the farmer/farming companies versus the nature compensation at the local level. It is a very intricate and detailed web of rules, including: the type of vegetation that can grow, the way in which soil should be left alone, but also under which conditions you can enter and destroy vegetation for example for the flow of water, sheep on land. Similarly, In Switzerland, growers must have a green cover or a crop during the winter. Indeed, there are lot of regulations on water, regarding for example animal density and distance from certain rivers. There are also policy incentives to use less plant protection. Certain activities, such as seeding, covering soil, bare soil for x amount weeks, are obligatory for direct payment. [Int.10 businesses, Int.15 businesses]. Int. 11 [scientific community] also underlines that there are no schemes for reduced tillage or something like this, because cover crop is the focus. Indeed, when farmers have organic farm, they get certain subsidies, but it is not specific on soil health, rather this is basically just to cover crops. Now agroforestry has also been established, but it is more a holistic practice. In Switzerland, there are 15/20 programs run through the canton and the Federation often helps with a certain percentage of money [Int.10 businesses]. Int.15 [businesses] also argues that in Switzerland there are measures which policy farmers can take, but

they are not really incentives to really look at the soil. Indeed, these measures do not work in practice, cost quite higher and do not benefit the system change.

In Sardinia (Italy), Int.4 [businesses] believed that the financial incentive tools for companies through income support measures is the main beneficial instrument for soil health. These instruments, which are directed at farms, are different. Today, they are essentially all contained within a general instrument called 'Programma di Sviluppo Rurale PSR' (Rural Development Plan).¹⁹¹ Indeed, in the program, there is a focus on protection, defense and safeguard of the soil resource, biodiversity, and the environment in general. In particular, in the latest PSR Sardinia (2014-2022), a sub-measure was activated which is called 10.1.1 'Difesa del Suolo' and is the title of the measure and soil protection.¹⁹² This measure is addressed to all agricultural companies that have arable land and therefore must be classified as arable land or use conservative agricultural practices (for example sowing on the ground and resting in rotation). The companies that join have the obligation for 5 years. There are some very explicit measures, the so-called functionality criteria are referred to. Int. 5 [businesses] explains that the PSR is a measure which allowed the so-called minimum work only on certain surfaces by receiving a premium of 220 euros. Int. 5 [businesses] consider this purpose clearly economical, especially for those leading companies in goat cheese which produce cereals from grain or in annual or biennial rotation. From a side they receive the prize of 200 euros per hectare and from the other side they produce the raw materials they need to feed the livestock. Therefore, it had to be of a dual culture of respect for the soil so that there is a regeneration of organic substance. Deep tillage retained fertility is improved over time through tillage and rotation. The two economic aspects are that of using the raw materials produced to feed one's own livestock and decreasing the share of external purchases of raw materials. There is also the possibility of adding the two measures of soil protection and organic farming which reduce the use of synthetic chemical products.

In Spain, in different places such as schools, food purchase is made in terms of sustainability by purchasing those producers who do short channel regenerative agriculture and environmental issues. It has been promoted by the EU and there are more projects in this sense to finance producers who are doing it well. There is also a brand that differentiates extensive livestock farming from industrial livestock farming that allows consumers, when they buy meat or cheese, to know what type of livestock model they are supporting and that is also an economic opportunity [Int.12 scientific community].

This year, Lithuania has adopted the Order of the minister related to the sustainable use of soil and some activities involve the Minister of Health and all environmental ministers.¹⁹³ The problem how to deal with their responsibilities between Ministers [Int.6 policy maker]. For soil health, Lithuania invest in the National plan which will help in asking for scientists how to measure for farmers, what is the best benefit for farmers to have a healthy soil, better environmental and economic conditions.¹⁹⁴ It is important to have consultations, explain to farmers because many of them were not very big production, but not to keep their environment. Our farmers even if they went to do monitoring for themselves, it costs money. Int.7 [farmer/land manager] refers to Croatian National

policy which is organized in a way that only the big farms, entrepreneurs will only see main benefits from policies which is according to soil health because they can in short period invest in machines organizing in another way the production they have.¹⁹⁵ Some small and middle farmers at the beginning cannot just in one or two-year transfer to another production policy because they do not have resources and they do not know what will happen with those investments.

Int.13 [policy maker] pointed out that since 1998 an ordinance of soil protection started mainly due to the pollution with heavy metals.¹⁹⁶ In general Switzerland has a three-value system for many of chemical pollution: guide, trigger and clean-up values. The guide values help to apply measures for precautionary soil protections. The trigger values imply that when there is an impact on food plants or forage plants, the canton government has to do something against. The so-called clean up involves replacing the soil, because it is really harmful than for any use. Switzerland also has a value for soil erosion, but not for soil compaction or area any other threat. The soil protection on construction sites is originally a collaboration of administration science and practice.¹⁹⁷ The Swiss Soil Science Society organises courses with a certificate and there are specialists of soil protection on construction sites.¹⁹⁸ The Canton gives permission for construction and it can oblige to involve a specialist who observes protection of construction sites. The whole soil protection during construction is then under the guidance of this protection specialist. In addition, Switzerland has this value in case of repeated soil erosion on agricultural land and it is possible to cut the direct payment. It has two systems of direct payments for agriculture, but this is hardly applied because the cantons do not have enough staff to follow this up. There are some ecological compliance orders for which farmers have to support also some of these friendly practices. The details about what they finance exactly depend on the canton.

This subsection underlines that there is not an overarching instrument for the protection of soil health either at national or EU level. In this context, the EU CAP and national eco scheme are identified as the main instrument. However, participants also share some expected positive elements coming from the expected Carbon Removal Scheme and the Nature Restoration Law.

3.2.3 Barriers and challenges in implementing soil health policies and economic instruments

After having discussed benefits and opportunities of policies and/or financial mechanisms on soil health, this subsection reflects on the implementation of those mechanisms particularly focusing on barriers and challenges. Table X shows that lobbies is the main common barrier or challenge identified by the experts, followed by politics and money/knowledge.

In Italy, the trade associations sit at the tables and want expensive compensatory measures, the bonus, they want those one-stop measures, that welfare system that supplements the income, that unproductive areas are in any case presided over by the presence of the farmer or shepherd. However, they also create a sort of habituation to contribution, to welfare and in some way, they dampen a bit of the entrepreneurial spirit that should be typical of those who do business [Int.4

businesses]. In Netherlands, the farming lobby is the biggest barrier or challenge [Int.9 Scientific community]. There are loads of different farmers, hence it is important to recognize the farmers who are struggling for their livelihood and the small farmers, but also a lot of farmers that are essentially businessmen and women, they're millionaires because they make a lot of profit. Loads of former members of the government go to work for farming organizations. Therefore, that has a huge effect on maintaining the status quo rather than opening up the real debate about where to go. The power of the status quo comes with land ownership finance which involves first financialization and then after even securitization. Int.15 [businesses] believes that Swiss decision makers have to rely on other sources or other people, which makes it easier for lobbying. Moreover, Int.13 [policy maker] points out that Soil sealing is a huge challenge because construction lobby is as strong as the farmer lobby. In Spain, Int.3 [scientific community] affirms that the interests of certain large corporations in agriculture do not coincide with the common interest in soil conservation. Corporations have great economic and political lobbying power over decisions at the European level as well. Some corporations in the use, in this case of synthetic herbicides, are generating contamination of soils and aquifers, and also the health of people, etc. In the story of the differentiation of extensive and intensive livestock farming, there is a conflict of interests between the same reasons. The ranchers, who are driving the most economy, are the industrial big manufacturers and for the industrial sector, hence the agrarian unions, for example, and the ministry itself do not make that differentiation and small, extensive livestock farming families do not have the economic capacity to lobby their unions, etc., in defence of these more sustainable practices.

Barriers and challenges in implementing soil health policies and economic instruments.	Italy (LL1)	Switzerland (LL2)	Netherlands (LL3)	Spain (LH1, LH2, LH3)	Croatia (LH4)	Lithuania (LH5)	Latvia (LH6)
Politics	x	x					
Business credit and conservation techniques application	x						
Premium measures and compensation paradox	x						

Not clear methodology		x					
Different soil structures		x					
Money and knowledge		x		x	x		
Maintain or increase soil organic carbon		x					
Lobbies	x	x	x	x			
Communication		x					
Farmers by their own and in groups				x			
Social lack of information				x			
Not clear how measure co-benefits				x			
Very poor structure of the farms					x		
Old age of farmers					x		
Addiction to governmental support					x		
Low profitability old guys					X		
Low education farmers					X		
Lack of knowledge of green practices					x		
Small fields: lots of owners, no farmers					X		
Expensive monitoring						x	

Lack of data							x
Mentality							x
Data harmonization							x
Too much EU level orientation							x
No contact between policy and science							x

Table 6 Barriers and challenges in implementing soil health policies and economic instruments.

In Italy, the first enemy to face is politics, because interests are very often a bit behind the scenes [Int.4 businesses]. As regards the experience of Rural Development Plans, it would be enough to stop talking about tools designed in other places and for other production contexts and to lower them a little more into the corporate production context where they must then be applied. Subsequently we have to fight with politics, for the rest it concerns precisely policies on the soil. In Switzerland, for many years, soil has been neglected. Biodiversity was a big issue, but the climate change issue has increased the political discussion on soil being part of the solution also for lack of water and water retention. Therefore, soil is now more repeating the focus of the politicians and it is a good period to carry out projects on soil topics [Int.10 businesses]. In Switzerland, Int.11 [scientific community] reflects on the fact that the last thing which is always a case for all of the policies is just a question how much money to give into a true cost accounting so to save for our food production and how much policy to spend on practices that really improve the situation. In Croatia, there is a problem of knowledge about these new green practices, because farmers are more than 60 years old and poorly educated [Int.7 farmer/landowner]. Therefore, any implementation of new practices/technologies is very difficult. Before the green policies, the government paid for farmers just to produce anything and without any knowledge or evaluation of the quality or yields etc. and, because of the low profitability, they were addicted for that kind of support. Nowadays, this is cut off and the government asked them to involve new practices green practices and they will pay for it. However, farmers previously got money without that, hence for them, it is difficult to adopt new practices. Moreover, these practices will probably cost more, or farmers will have lower yields, hence they will try to avoid that. So that is also a problem of knowledge about these new green practices. Int.7 [farmer/landowner] reflects on the fact that in Croatia there are small fields and a lot of owners, but not farmers, hence the problem is how to organize some steps to get better soil quality and health. The barriers are thus the very poor structure of farms and if farmers are not the owners of the land, they do not use it properly [Int.1 scientific community].

In Spain, there is not only a lack of information not only of decision-makers, but also the social lack of information on these aspects is the biggest barrier [Int.8 scientific community]. There is no debate on soil and misinformation such as the need of glyphosate for regenerating the soil. In Spain, in the

last 10 years, the farmers, the rangers, etc are implementing their own better practices in order to prevent the problems of erosion and desertification thanks to the CAP in terms of regional or state policies, but they are implementing them on their own [Int.2 scientific community].

In Switzerland, Int.13 [policy maker] points out that it is very difficult to maintain or increase soil organic carbon in soils. Indeed, in normal mineral soils, this may be possible if you do agriculture with good practices, but if you do agriculture on organic soils peatland, it is not possible. The opposition comes saying that they didn't know from the land uses and the Farmers Association that they cannot install such an article in our ordinance. In Switzerland and Spain, one of the biggest challenges is that the methodology is not clear [Int.11 scientific community, Int.12 scientific community]. Regarding carbon sequestration, it is not clear how the carbon will be captured in the soil in the short/medium and long term, and this is extremely challenging for the policymakers. Indeed, in order to implement certain schemes, a method needs to measure, verify and ensure that the carbon and the improvements are kept for a long time. In the last centuries, schemes have been considered as one fitting all solutions, but farms and soil structures are very different in the European Union and in Switzerland. Therefore, it is very challenging to implement practices which are just for everybody. How measuring those co-benefits is challenging in Spain [Int.12 scientific community]. Indeed, the carbon balance depends on different factors and it's not always easy to have a methodology that works for every region every area every farm, because it depends on the type of soil, on the type of farming practices, what the farmer does or does on, what the weather is that they are and then to have any scheme of it followed methodologies.

In Latvia and at EU level, data harmonization is an issue and definitions are differing among different sources. For example, if data for target setting for restoration of agricultural organic soil is taken from National greenhouse gas inventory, policymakers should understand that different definitions are used among countries. Indeed, one country starts organic soil from 20 cm of peat layer, another starts from 40 cm. This issue refers to is source data and data quality. Another problem is that data outcome may work at EU level, but not at national level. The problem is if remote sensing data are not used as wide as possible. If policymakers are not in close contact with science, you cannot have good data and you cannot come up with good decisions. Indeed, a lack of the data can be named as the most prominent barrier or challenge [Int.4 policy maker]. It is not easy discussing with farmers and foresters and difficult time with implementing a past sustainability tool for nutrients as part of CAP. Sometimes, farmers request information again and again. This could be a problem also in soil health and it is important how policy makers will work with farmers and forests in this data gathering and how they will use cross-sectoral databases as much as possible to avoid double requesting of information from landowners. People are also afraid that sharing information could cost them some charges or penalties later if something comes out that something is not done in accordance to do some national or EU legislation. Indeed, mentality could be an issue as well.

In Lithuania, the finance guidelines are used like for sustainable management for soil but not for the monitoring or for soil sampling. There are only a couple of accredited Laboratories, and they are very expensive [Int.6 policy maker].

In Italy, business credit and conservation techniques application are identified as barriers/challenges [Int.5 businesses]. Indeed, the farmer's income support today should be accompanied in this transition path that is truly convenient because today it is not mandatory, but optional. In the future, this prize will most likely not be there, but the companies should be ready. These rewards must be proportionate, and they must be educational, because as companies are not used to it, not having this mentality, we are unlikely to be able to involve them. To accompany the entrepreneur, he must have tools and educational measures. Premium measures and compensation are a paradoxical mechanism. It was done on the basis of income, but the paradox is that rich agriculture helps more rather than practices such as conservative agriculture where they can also have costs, for example, with fuel consumption. The problem lies in the obligation of rotation which very often leads to a reduction in income for the agricultural entrepreneur. If the measurement paradigm shifts from lost income to the evaluation of ecosystem services, then indeed the value of the shepherd who raises sheep in depopulated areas and continues to cultivate in areas.

The data gathered showed that there are more than twenty barriers or challenges in the implementation phase of mechanisms that protect, rehabilitate, and restore soil health. Lobbies and politics are the main barriers both at national and EU level. In addition, lack of sources such money and knowledge have a significant impact on the implementation of those instruments.

3.2.4 Trade-offs and synergies in the development and implementation of policies and economic instruments that take into account protection, rehabilitation and restoration of soil

After having discussed barriers and challenges for the implementation of those mechanisms particularly focusing on barriers and challenges, this subsection identifies trade-offs and synergies in the development and implementation of policies and economic instruments that take into account protection, rehabilitation and restoration of soil. As Table 7 highlights, co-benefits and educational programs are the main common trade-offs and synergies identified by participants.

In Switzerland, Int. 13 [policymaker] refers to lots of co-benefits related to a better soil quality. Soil productivity is also better, if the water retention capacity and the protection against other threats, like landslides and floods, are also increased by the regulation. On the broader scale, Int. 15 [businesses] also affirms that healthy soils lead to healthy humans. Indeed, plants can absorb more micronutrients when there is a healthy soil and that would make vegetables for example tastier and more micronutrient dense. This would lead to less money to be spent in health and as a state. In Croatia, Int.1 [scientific community] believes that there should be many benefits from the implementation of mechanisms for soil health, but this needs very much effort in terms of knowledge and money. In Spain, Int.12 [scientific community] identifies many synergies even from socio-economical point of view and for instance for health. Even from the climate change the point of view, restoring soil health will allow to keep greenhouse gas emissions stored which means a

good quality of the health for everybody. Even from the socio economical point of view, the secondary use of the biomass will allow more organic matter in the soil.

In Switzerland, Int.11 [scientific community] points out educational programs in the schools as a significant synergy. Indeed, children and young people really learn to understand the necessities of soil and why soil is important and how it actually provides food and how they can take care as a consumer or as an individual person to contribute to healthy soils. An opportunity could be to really involve art into soil health programs as well. Indeed, there are some existing programs such as sounding soils which is a good way to make people understand the importance of soil. Therefore, it would be useful to mainstream the topic into very different areas than just the agriculture sector. In Lithuania, Int. 6 [policy maker] highlights the education of farmers to apply specific practices which support the protection and conservation of soil. Moreover, education is useful for farmers to receive incentives for using a specific species on the land on the soil so they can maintain biodiversity. There should be advice services, more formal consultations for farmers.

Trade-offs and synergies	Italy (LL1)	Switzerland (LL2)	Netherlands (LL3)	Spain (LH1, LH2, LH3)	Croatia (LH4)	Lithuania (LH5)	Latvia (LH6)
Synergies between institutions	x						
Economic compromise	x						
Infrastructure policy		x					
Climate change		x					
Educational programs		x				x	
Conflict between plowing the soil and reduced plant protection products application.		x					
Co-benefits (socio-economical, health)		x		x	x		

Yields and financial needs		x					
plant production about fungicides and insecticides		x					
Individual and group working of farmers		x					
legislation regulatory Frameworks made to empower local communities			x				
Certification of carbon removals				x			
Share knowledge across countries				x			
Biosphere Reserve Agrarian Contract				x			
Collaboration among different instruments		x				x	
Three sustainability pillars							x

Table 7 Trade-offs and synergies in the development and implementation of policies and economic instruments that take into account protection, rehabilitation and restoration of soil.

In Switzerland, Int.11 [scientific community] affirms that there are opportunities of synergies between with farming policies and environmental policies. In Lithuania, Int.6 [policy maker] explains that they are exploring collaboration among different instruments to be planned and implemented with the aim of supporting the conservation and protection of soil health. In Switzerland, Int.11 [scientific community] and Int.13 [policy maker] highlight conflicts and trade-offs with policies for infrastructure. Indeed, there is a huge problem to keep the agricultural land, because a lot of the that has been annually transferred to building and construction sites. Int.13 [policy maker] also points out the conflict between plowing the soil and reduced plant protection products application, because there is this measure of conservation agriculture which forbid plowing the soil to maintain

and protect soil structure and life. Another example of trade-off is the use of biochar which is now regarded as a measure against climate change. It consists of putting organic carbon into the soil through biochar, but it is still uncertain the effect on soil biology.

In Italy, Int.4 [businesses] points out synergy between institutions (universities, regional institutes, other public bodies) for the protection of the soil which must arise from knowledge which can no longer be the old geological map. There is now a need for more in-depth studies, which are carried out on a smaller scale. The region should finance types of studies on important areas from an agronomic point of view, because they are tools that become useful for everyone including those who physically go to work and suggest to farmers what to do.

In Spain, Int.3 [scientific community] refers to synergies between the different countries to share knowledge.

In Latvia, Int.4 [policy maker] stresses the significance of having an overall view on all three sustainability pillars. Indeed, just looking at one or two pillars, undermines discussions with local people and at the end with implementation as well. Society is usually quite open to environmental issues and they understand the importance, but they are still oriented to the fact that it is still their land and they want to get economic income. Social dimension is also very often overlooked in terms of what would be the impact on workplaces, even on environment for looking from a social perspective. A lack of information about technologies and additional bureaucracy in data gathering lead to lose trust of landowners.

In Switzerland, Int.10 [businesses] underlines that the individual work of farmers on their field is the most important. From there, farmers get the motivation to be active also in working groups and coming together until all farmers get more sensitive to certain issues. Regarding that movement of regenerative agriculture, it is often more or less blind application of new recipes, whereas a strategy should be applied based on previous observations.

In Italy, Int.5 [businesses] highlights the economic compromise to ensure that the prizes are truly attractive, especially in the first phase. Indeed, these prizes should support multinationals to direct their production towards a new medium-long term investment path. This means that multinationals are rewarded if they use synthetic chemical products as long as they are accompanied by the use of control and prediction tools. In Croatia, Int.7 [farmer/land manager] also refers to some subsidies and capital investments. However, the policy is changing every four year and then came another one on the national level. Hence. There is a problem with property of lands.

In Switzerland, Int.15 [businesses] identify yields and financial needs as trade-offs. Sometimes more herbicides are needed, but Switzerland has a fixed pot of money, hence every new policy will make other policies lose money. In terms of plant production, there are big synergies about fungicides and insecticides.

In Netherlands, Int.9 [scientific community] reflects on regulatory frameworks to empower local communities, such as the energy communities in Italy. The European Union is trying to standardize these initiatives as much as possible. However, too much regulation and standardization work against these local initiatives because they must fulfil a certain framework that does not necessarily

fits for the local context. At the same time, there is still a fear of letting go too much. Therefore, these initiatives work very well because they happen at the relatively small scale, but it becomes very difficult when they are applied at national or European level, because that would need standardization.

In Spain, Int.2 [land manager] points out that the EU certification of carbon removals is really expected, because now there are voluntary carbon markets, which are very uncertain. About carbon credit, the opportunity can increase from a first low level in terms of fertility of organic material. Indeed, this increase in the carbon credits is dramatic. Farmers are uncertain if that is really a good opportunity or if it is better to wait for the regulation to get a better price. Moreover, they are concerning about what happens if they get this contract with companies in terms of CAP, because if they also apply for the eco scheme, they receive a subsidy to sequester carbon. Therefore, farmers would receive a double payment, one from the CAP and a payment from this carbon credits company. All these questions persuade the farmers to sign the contracts with these companies which manage the carbon credits for the voluntary carbon markets. The problem is that farmers do not know if this benefit in the short term will last in the long term.

Int.8 [scientific community] explains that in Menorca they had this Biosphere Reserve Agrarian Contract which was using CAP funds to accompany the farmers to make a transition, by improving the whole management of the local resources, mainly soil water and biodiversity.¹⁹⁹ The farmer used to identify good practices jointly with an inspector and the funds were provided according to the improvement of the protection realised. This can seem very complicated at the European level. Indeed, only 5% of the beneficiaries of CAP gets an inspection. This could be like a way of following up the improvement in the area and also it can be analysed by areas and/or with internal control system of cooperatives. There was a proposal at the Spanish level and some regions to protect soils with high value and link them to certain conditions of farming and then there are all the solar panels in the best soils.

Participants identified many co-benefits in the development and implementation of policy and economic instruments for the healthy soil, for example, from a socio-economic perspective. Education programmes for general society and farmers are also critical in order to create such synergies.

3.3 Conclusions

This section explored the main types of soil pressures and soil degradation that participants from LLs and LHs related countries have identified as significant in their areas of experience and sectors. Although, countries are currently experiencing many different soil pressures, results show that erosion and contamination/pollution are the main soil pressures considered by participants. The section also discussed benefits and opportunities of policy and economic instruments contributing to the protection, rehabilitation, and restoration of soil health at multiple levels. The EU CAP and related national eco schemes are the main instrument mentioned by participants who reflected on

different benefits and opportunities, including: maximizing profit while respecting the environment; subsidies for green/crop cover, direct payments for agriculture; orchard cover soil management; mandatory carbon stock measurement; agriculture conservation; biodiversity protection; sustainability tool; soil analysis; restoration activities. Participants also examined barriers and challenges in the implementation of those mechanisms, particularly such as lobbies, politics, money, and knowledge. Co-benefits and educational programs are the main trade-offs and synergies in the development and implementation of policies and economic instruments that take into account protection, rehabilitation and restoration of soil.

This analysis will extrapolate and generalise the evidence gathered for the use in other contexts, by identifying a series of general recommendations in the following section.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

This section will draw the main conclusions of the study and provide an outlook of the expected European legislative steps towards the protection of soil health (Section 4.1). Moreover, the section will list some recommendations for the LLs and LHs to better understand legal, policy and economic instruments for the protection of soil health and their implementation (Section 4.2). Finally, a summary of the main conclusions will also be provided.

4.1 Expected European legislative steps

Based on the mapping review of European, national, and regional policy requirements and incentives aiming at or encouraging management of investment in soil health and on the semi-structured interviews with experts and representatives of organizations involved in implementing the scheme, expected European legislative steps are outlined below.

Soil Monitoring System

Considering the Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience⁷⁹, EU legislation should identify the indicators for soil health. Indeed, EU consists of different countries which have different organizations in charge of monitoring with a different understanding of soil health. Moreover, not only indicator, but various indicators can specify a bad condition. Indeed, monitoring should not consider only heavy metals, but also some soil biology indicators. In other words, monitoring should open it up more for other soil threats like soil erosion, soil compaction, soil sealing, a new pollution as well, issues like microplastic, Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances (PFAS), plant protection products. Furthermore, monitoring implies considering enough observation sites where check soil quality periodically. Indeed, measuring one little plot does not mean that soil in all regions is in bad condition. In this context, soil mapping should not cover only agricultural land, but also forests, urban areas and so on, but this process is time consuming. Moreover, farmers will also need money

for monitoring. Therefore, EU should consider how to involve them in the design of a monitoring system.

Soil Data Harmonization

Since definitions are differing among different sources, policymakers need harmonized data to serve as a common knowledge base on the state of the soil health. At EU level, different definitions are used among countries. For example, one country starts organic soil from 20 centimetres of a peat layer, and another starts from 40 centimetres. Therefore, those data are not really comparable at the end. Moreover, some EU database may not work at national level, for example, if a country is not investing in possibilities to operate with remote sensing data. Moreover, it is important how policymakers will work with farmers and foresters in this data gathering and how they will use cross-sector databases as much as possible to avoid double-requesting information from landowners. For example, with the implementation of farm sustainability tool for nutrients, as part of CAP landowners, holders of agricultural farms, protested very heavily that additional information was requested like twice or information is not together from sources of origin.

EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)⁵² has different ways to face soil health which are not only according to all different Member States contexts, but rather they are always in terms of the wider Europe context. For this reason, EU legislation should support Member States to have a proper policy, in terms of erosion, loss of soil fertility, droughts, and not only with punctual aids or subsidies. However, some groups that get most benefit from the CAP wants to keep it as it is so they continue to get most of the funds. Indeed, almost every CAP beneficiary can do the improved conditionality in CAP and apply at least for one eco scheme, hence CAP is just paying for what it has already done without accompanying to a transition. The current CAP has also helped the concentration of land and farming rights in fewer hands, which means that in most territories, it's not actually farms, but companies. Therefore, EU should build a culture of being aware of the importance to protect soil not only for the crops that people get now, but also for the future. EU should support converting those payments to really practices which are sustainable and which are supporting those ones that lead to a reduced cost in the future. This would be a first and essential step instead of subsidizing those that are currently harmful for the environment and producing a lot of societal costs now and in the future. The European Commission already has a proposal to change the logic of the CAP and also have more transferral policies that start with the soil health because it has an impact on the rest of the chain. Finally, the laws need to be compliant because in some cases there is not a control of the compliance of the laws, for example the conditionality in the CAP.

Organic regulation

Organic regulation should be more strict in terms of how to manage the soil. The same regulation should not be applied for Mediterranean countries as it does for Northern European countries,

because the context is completely different. There should be a rule which regulates how to implement better practices or how to maybe even ban some practices in agriculture, in terms of how to keep a better health of the soils. Indeed, nowadays, for example, in Spain organic olive trees farms are not found without a huge problem in terms of erosion. Organic farming should increase the fertility and increase the health of soil. Although there are recommendations and obviously some best practice to try, it is not enough for major running countries.

EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework

Since the EU Commission proposal about carbon removal certification²⁰⁰ has not started yet, farmers are uncertain on whether the short term benefit from signing contracts with carbon credits companies will still be a benefit in the long term. Moreover, farmers are unsure about if there will be any problems with CAP, since they may already receive a subsidy under an eco-scheme. For this reason, it is crucial to have the regulation as soon as possible, to really know how to deal with, what the opportunities are, and also what data to provide. Additionally, the methodology of carbon sequestration is not clear. This means that it is unsure how short, long -term, medium -term, the carbon will be captured in the soil. This is extremely challenging for the policymakers if they want to implement certain schemes. A method is needed to measure, verify and ensure at a later stage that the carbon and the improvements are kept for a long time. For this reason, the EU Commission needs to set up new methodologies. Usually, soil-carbon sequestration is also mainly related to the policy targets of the climate from the national governments. This means that it is not quantified how much soil-carbon sequestration should increase within the next few years. However, some measures have been set, such as, for example, reducing cultivation on peat soils and using animal manure on fields. Moreover, there is no a clear goal on the soil erosion topic, but rather certain practices for increasing soil -carbon sequestration. Additionally, peatlands must be included in the certification, but also wildlands. The carbon removal certification framework should also include soil health parameters. Indeed, the EU Commission is trying to explain how to score projects that improve the sustainability criteria for biodiversity and for water, for adaptation and mitigation to climate change, the so co-benefits. Soil health needs to be part of those criteria. However, the EU Commission should address the cost of implementing such projects, including certifying a project and going ahead through all the steps.

EU Nature Restoration Law

The recent approval of the Nature Restoration Law²⁰¹ saw the postponement of the glyphosate use during the next decade. Glyphosate is used in the agriculture sector, therefore it has an enormous impact on agrarian ecosystems, including soil health. Indeed, within the Nature Restoration Law and the Habitat Directive¹⁹⁰, the agricultural or livestock management is essential for the conservation of some ecosystems. Therefore, EU legislation should further address those soil pressures.

4.2 Recommendations for the LLs and LHs

The analysis of multilevel policy and economic mechanisms for soil health and of the data retrieved from the semi-structured interviews highlighted some main issues upon which the following recommendations for LLs and LHs have been elaborated.

- The definition of soil health is indefinite across international, EU and national level. For these reasons, there is not a single policy and economic instrument, but rather many instruments with direct and indirect impact on soil health. Therefore, since the relevant regulation is not specified, LLs and LHs should consider any instruments in order to protect, restore and rehabilitate soil health.
- In terms of policy, the protection of new soil is disconnected. This means that most policy instruments deal with pollution abatement, while there is a little understanding of soil reproduction capacity.
- Policy and economic instruments are applied mainly in ways to rework soil for agriculture or cover. However, dedicated mechanisms are lacking for integrity wildfire, water supply, industrial politics, urbanization, reuse of degraded soil.
- In terms of monitoring and data gathering, more public expenditure is required in order to assist farmers in measuring soil health.
- In terms of envisioning liability, generally, landowners and farmers who uses and works on soil should take care for the next generation. However, government or state should have to be more involved in the protection of the law of the land, by undertaking some kind of regular analysis and not just chemical, but also physical and ecological analysis of the soil. Politicians are supposed to be representative of the society, but the society itself can have their own role for a healthy soil. For example, not only organic, but any consumers could include in their decision-making process the better practices of the farmers in terms of soil health. If society invest public funds to this transition, farmers benefit from it and also the damage is not externalised to other regions.

4.3 Summary

This section outlined how European legislation should ensure the protection, restoration, and rehabilitation of soil health, through effective and efficient monitoring systems, data harmonization, CAP, organic regulation, carbon removal certification framework and nature restoration law. In general, a specific law on soil health is needed. Indeed, since the definition of soil health is not harmonized, nor countries regulations are. For this reason, an overarching legislation will better connect and integrate all the current instruments that have impact on soil. Moreover, it is essential to control that there is compliance on that law. A better understanding of soil reproduction capacity is also critical to maintain healthy soil. Policy and economic mechanisms should be applied not only

in the agriculture sector, but also in other relevant sectors, such as water. Finally, land users have a lot of responsibility for soil health, but regulation and administrations make sure that they fulfil them. However, the horizontal regulation is rarely even implemented.

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